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Probabilities of Allen Interval Relations

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in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of

Bachelor in Arts (Moderatorship)
in Computer Science, Linguistics and a Language

Supervisor: Dr Tim Fernando

May 2025

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Probabilities of Allen Interval Relations

Cillín Forrester, Bachelor in Arts (Moderatorship)
in Computer Science, Linguistics and a Language
University of Dublin, Trinity College, 2025

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This project investigates probabilistic extensions of Allen's Interval Algebra, a formal framework for reasoning about temporal intervals and their relationships. By integrating temporal logic with stochastic modelling, it explores how uncertainty can be incorporated into the algebra's classical structure. Key hypotheses concerning the behaviour and distribution of interval relations are evaluated using simulation, statistical testing, and interactive visualisation. The resulting framework offers a foundation for reasoning about time in uncertain contexts, with potential applications in fields such as natural language processing, artificial intelligence, and temporal databases.

Freedom is what you do with what's been done to you.

— *Jean-Paul Sartre*

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CILLÍN FORRESTER

University of Dublin, Trinity College
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Chapter 1

Introduction

Accurate representation of time and temporal relationships is critical in both human reasoning and computational systems. Time intervals and their qualitative temporal relations are fundamental in many areas of computer science, from scheduling and planning to natural language understanding. James F. Allen’s seminal work, published in 1983, defined a set of 13 basic relations that can hold between any two time intervals (e.g., *before*, *during*, *overlaps*, etc.). Allen’s Interval Algebra provides an exhaustive and mutually exclusive categorisation of interval relationships, forming the basis for qualitative temporal reasoning. Traditionally, these relations have been used in a deterministic manner (an interval either definitely *meets* another or it does not), but an emerging question is: how likely is each relation to occur under a given random process of interval generation? In classical Allen Algebra, relations are binary (they either definitely hold or not); here we instead ask: given randomly generated intervals, what *distribution* of relations emerges?

This report investigates the **prior probabilities of Allen interval relations under stochastic timeline models**. In particular, we consider a probabilistic *birth–death model* in which intervals begin (“are born”) and end (“die”) with certain probabilities at each time step. By adjusting the birth probability p and death probability q , we can simulate different regimes of timeline dynamics – from very sparse timelines (low p , high q , yielding mostly non-overlapping intervals) to very dense timelines (high p , low q , yielding many overlapping intervals). Under such settings, each pair of intervals that occurs has some probability of realising each of Allen’s 13 relations. A primary goal of this work is to empirically estimate these probabilities for various (p, q) conditions and to analyse how the distribution of relations changes as the timeline dynamics vary.

Beyond pairwise relations, temporal reasoning often involves *composition* of relations: given interval A is related to B in some way and B to C in another, what can be deduced about the relation between A and C ? In Allen’s algebra, this is handled

by a deterministic composition table (e.g., if A *meets* B and B *overlaps* C , then A can only *precede* C in the qualitative sense). Under uncertainty, however, $A-C$ could turn out to be any of the 13 relations with some probability distribution. This project extends the analysis to such **probabilistic composition** of Allen relations. We perform large-scale Monte Carlo simulations to estimate the distribution of $A-C$ relations for each possible pair (R_1, R_2) of preceding relations $A-B = R_1$ and $B-C = R_2$. This yields a 13×13 probabilistic composition matrix for each (p, q) setting, providing insight into how uncertainty propagates through relational composition.

The primary research objectives of this work can be enumerated as:

1. Computing $P(R)$ for each of Allen’s 13 relations under our stochastic interval model across different parameter settings
2. Developing a probabilistic extension to Allen’s composition table by computing $P(R_3 \mid R_1, R_2)$ for all relation triples
3. Providing interactive visualisation tools for exploring these probabilities and their dependencies on model parameters

To facilitate exploration and visualisation of these concepts, we developed an interactive web application using the Dash framework. Users can adjust the parameters (p, q) and interact with three primary modules: (1) **Relation Simulation**, which displays the frequency of the 13 interval relations under the chosen probabilities; (2) **Composition Analysis**, which reports — for any pair of relations (e.g., what $A-C$ relations can arise when A *overlaps* B and B *starts* C ?) — the probability distribution over all 13 possible outcomes; and (3) **Matrix Analysis**, which visualises the full composition-probability matrix together with summary statistics such as entropy, the Gini index, and divergence from reference models.

In summary, this project contributes a thorough study of Allen interval relations under uncertainty, including:

- A Monte Carlo simulation engine exploring the parameter space of birth–death processes, generating empirical probabilities for Allen’s relations across timeline dynamics
- Quantitative analysis employing information theory and inequality metrics to characterise relation distributions across parameter settings
- Probabilistic extensions to Allen’s composition table, quantifying how uncertainties propagate through chains of relations

- An interactive analytical environment for visualising and exploring temporal relation probabilities and their compositional properties¹

Our findings reveal that relation probabilities vary systematically with timeline dynamics, with entropy measures peaking at specific (p, q) configurations; composition outcomes show predictable biases even under uncertainty; and information-theoretic metrics provide insights into the structure of temporal reasoning. These contributions advance both the theoretical understanding and practical application of probabilistic temporal reasoning.

The remainder of this report is structured as follows. Chapter 2 reviews relevant background and related work, including Allen’s Interval Algebra and prior research on probabilistic temporal relations. Chapter 3 defines the problem formally and outlines the design of our approach, including the model and system architecture. Chapter 4 details the implementation of the simulation engine and web application. Chapter 5 presents experimental results, evaluating the relation probability distributions and composition outcomes across different scenarios and comparing them with theoretical expectations. Finally, Chapter 6 concludes the report, discussing key findings, limitations, and avenues for future work.

¹The application was accessible at allen-interval.onrender.com at the time of publication.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

2.1 Allen’s Interval Algebra

Temporal reasoning has been a subject of extensive study for decades. Allen’s Interval Algebra (1983) laid the groundwork by introducing the 13 qualitative interval relations, which are *distinct* (no two relations can hold simultaneously between the same intervals) and *exhaustive* (for any two definite intervals, exactly one of the 13 relations applies). These relations describe all possible ways two time intervals can be arranged relative to each other, as illustrated in Table 2.1.

The remaining six relations are the converses of the first six (typically denoted with capital letters: P, M, O, S, D, F), representing the same relationships but with the intervals reversed. For example, if A *precedes* (p) B, then B is *preceded by* (P) A.

Allen’s work also provided a composition table specifying, for any two relations $R_1 = A-B$ and $R_2 = B-C$, the set of possible $A-C$ relations that are consistent with R_1 and R_2 . This algebra enabled reasoning systems to propagate temporal constraints without committing to exact numeric times.

2.2 Probabilistic Extensions of Allen’s Algebra

While Allen’s framework is qualitative, later researchers explored the idea of assigning *prior probabilities* to these relations under various assumptions about how intervals occur.

2.2.1 Finite-Order Enumeration Approach

A notable approach by Fernando & Vogel (2019) considered all possible timelines (orders of interval start/end points) of a given size and computed the proportion of those timelines in which a given relation holds between two specific intervals. In effect, they enumerate

Table 2.1: Allen’s 7 fundamental interval relations with symbolic notation and visual representation

Symbol	Relation	Meaning	Visual Representation
p	precedes	A ends before B starts	
m	meets	A ends exactly when B starts	
o	overlaps	A starts before B, overlaps, ends before B ends	
s	starts	A starts with B but ends before B	
d	during	A starts after B starts and ends before B ends	
f	finishes	A starts after B but ends with B	
e	equals	A and B start and end at the same time	

the space of “finite temporality strings” – sequences of symbols representing interval start (\uparrow) and end (\downarrow) events – to derive the likelihood of relations. For example, for two intervals among n intervals placed randomly on a timeline, Fernando & Vogel showed that when $n = 2$ the 13 relations are all equally likely (each with probability $1/13$), whereas for larger n the distribution becomes non-uniform. Their work provided concrete probabilities for Allen relations in small cases and established that certain relations (like *equals*) remain relatively rare as n grows, while others (like *before/after*) become comparatively more common. This combinatorial enumeration approach offers an exact, if computationally intensive, way to calculate relation probabilities in finite cases. The resulting distribution, often referred to as the Fernando–Vogel (F–V) distribution in our analysis, serves as an important baseline for validating our simulation results.

2.2.2 Memoryless Birth-Death Process

Suliman (2021) developed a Python framework for simulating timeline generation using stochastic processes (building upon the concept of finite temporality strings) and computed

prior probabilities for Allen relations. This approach essentially treats the timeline as a random process and uses Monte Carlo simulation to estimate how often each relation occurs. Suliman’s framework confirmed known results (such as the uniform $1/13$ distribution for two purely random intervals) and extended analysis to more complex timelines, even incorporating real-world temporal data (e.g., TimeBank annotated events) to compare empirical frequencies.

The findings indicated that a simple memoryless birth/death process yields a characteristic distribution of relations. In fact, one specific outcome reported by Suliman is that under a memoryless model where intervals start and end with equal probability (analogous to our $p = 0.5, q = 0.5$ scenario), the resulting distribution of the 13 relations is highly symmetric: seven relations (the ones that describe one interval occurring entirely before, after, or just touching the other) each occur about $1/9$ of the time, and the remaining six (the ones involving partial overlap or containment) each occur about $1/27$ of the time. This matches the analytic expectations for a fully memoryless process and will serve as a validation point for our simulation results (we refer to this particular distribution as the *Suliman baseline* in later sections).

2.2.3 State-Dependent Interval Models

More recently, research has turned to more complex probabilistic models that go beyond the memoryless assumption. Petrukhin (2024) introduced a framework that extends the timeline generation model using *finite-state machines* to represent more complex event dynamics (sometimes called “granular” events). In his work, events are not just intervals with a birth and death, but can have internal states (such as a creature being *young* vs *old*) that influence their longevity. By superposing multiple finite-state automata, Petrukhin was able to simulate timelines where the probability of an interval ending (dying) could depend on how long it has been alive (its state).

This additional complexity was shown to “correct” some unintuitive results observed in simpler models. For instance, under the simple memoryless model, the relations *overlaps* and *during* (and their converses) tend to occur with roughly equal probability – essentially, there is symmetry between an event partially overlapping another and one event entirely nested during another. Petrukhin demonstrated that by using a two-state model (young vs old intervals with different death rates), one can break this symmetry in a controlled way. In a realistic configuration (where intervals have a higher chance to end once they become “old”), the probability of an overlap-type relation becomes higher than that of a during-type relation. Conversely, if one contrives an unnatural scenario (young intervals end very quickly but old intervals rarely die), the model produces the opposite effect:

during relations become more likely than *overlaps*. These results highlight that the distribution of Allen relations can be sensitive to the underlying assumptions about event durations and life cycles. Petrukhin’s FSM-based approach essentially generalises the birth-death process by adding state-dependent transition probabilities, thereby broadening the space of possible probability distributions for the relations.

2.3 Research Gap and Our Approach

Previous research has established important foundations for understanding the probabilistic nature of Allen relations. However, significant opportunities remain for advancing the field. In particular, whilst prior work has examined individual parameter settings, a systematic exploration of probabilistic composition across varying timeline dynamics has not been undertaken.

Our research contributes to the field in several important ways:

- Development of probabilistic composition tables for Allen’s interval algebra, extending traditional deterministic composition to account for uncertainty propagation
- Systematic analysis of the parameter space of timeline dynamics, revealing patterns in how relation probabilities vary with birth and death probabilities
- Application of information-theoretic metrics for characterising relation distributions, providing insight into their diversity and structural properties
- Implementation of an interactive analytical environment that facilitates exploration and visualisation of temporal relations under varying conditions

These contributions build upon and extend existing work. Where prior research established important baseline distributions and methodologies, our work maps the broader parameter space and addresses the previously unexamined dimension of probabilistic relation composition. The next chapter formalises the problem and outlines our approach in detail.

Chapter 3

Design

3.1 Problem Formulation

The core problem addressed in this report is to quantitatively characterise the likelihood of each of Allen’s interval relations under a parameterised stochastic model, and to determine how these probabilities compose when relations are chained. In more concrete terms:

1. We seek to compute $P(R)$ for each relation $R \in \{before, meets, overlaps, \dots\}$ given a generative process of intervals controlled by two parameters: p (the probability that a new interval begins at any given moment) and q (the probability that any given ongoing interval ends at that moment). These parameters define a simple birth–death process on a timeline.
2. We also seek to compute $P(R_3 \mid R_1, R_2)$ for all triples (R_1, R_2, R_3) of Allen’s relations, where R_1 is the relation between intervals A and B , R_2 is the relation between B and C , and R_3 is the resulting relation between A and C . In classical Allen algebra, R_3 would be constrained to a certain set given R_1 and R_2 ; here we want the full probability distribution over R_3 outcomes, again as a function of the model parameters p and q .

Solving this problem analytically for arbitrary p and q is intractable owing to the combinatorial explosion of possible timeline scenarios (especially for the composition part, which effectively involves three intervals and their six end-point events). Therefore, the approach taken is to use Monte Carlo simulation to approximate these probabilities. The task then becomes designing a simulation that can efficiently generate a large number of random interval configurations according to the (p, q) model and accurately tally the frequencies of each relation and composition outcome.

An important aspect of the problem is ensuring that our simulation and analysis framework is not only correct and efficient but also accessible for exploration. We want to enable interactive experimentation with different p and q values and immediate visualisation of how the relation probabilities change. This motivates the development of a web-based user interface where users (or the researcher) can adjust parameters and see results in real time, in addition to running large offline simulations for final analysis.

In summary, the design problem is two-fold:

1. **Design a stochastic simulation model** for interval generation that faithfully implements the desired birth/death probabilities and can collect statistics on Allen relations and their compositions.
2. **Design a user interface and data flow** that allows visualisation of these statistics in a clear manner (e.g., bar charts for single-relation distributions, matrix heat-maps for composition probabilities), and supports on-the-fly simulation for moderate sample sizes as well as loading of pre-computed results for high-precision analysis.

3.1.1 Identified Challenges

Several key challenges were identified in addressing the above problem:

- **Computational Complexity:** Accurately estimating probabilities for rare events (such as the *equals* relation) requires an extremely large number of simulation trials. For stable probability estimates, especially for relations that might occur with probability < 0.01 , millions of random interval generations are needed. This is computationally expensive if implemented naively. Moreover, to understand how these probabilities change across the parameter space, simulations must be run for many (p, q) combinations, further increasing the computational burden.
- **Ensuring Full Coverage:** With 13 relations and $13^2 = 169$ possible pairs for composition, some relation combinations might be extremely rare under certain (p, q) settings. For example, in a very sparse timeline (high q , low p), it's unlikely to observe two intervals that *overlap* each other. Similarly, for composition, seeing two consecutive *overlaps* relations in such a sparse regime would be rare. The challenge is obtaining a representative sample that covers all possibilities, especially for comparing distributions across parameter values.
- **Temporal Dependencies in Composition:** When simulating three intervals (A, B, C) to compute composition probabilities, these must be generated within

a single timeline where the temporal ordering is preserved. Simply generating independent pairs (A, B) and (B, C) would not correctly model the dependencies that arise from B being the “bridge” between A and C . The simulation must ensure that the generated triples accurately reflect the underlying stochastic process without introducing bias.

- **Real-time Interactivity vs Accuracy:** For an interactive web application, users expect immediate feedback when adjusting parameters. However, running sufficient trials (millions) to get accurate results is impractical for real-time interaction. Balancing the need for quick feedback with statistical reliability presents a significant challenge in the design of the user interface and computational backend.
- **Visualisation and User Experience:** Presenting a 13-category probability distribution or a 13×13 matrix in an intuitive, comprehensible way is non-trivial. Users need to quickly grasp which relations are dominant and how this changes with parameters. For composition analysis, they need to be able to focus on specific relation pairs without being overwhelmed by the full 169-cell matrix. Additionally, numerical summaries such as entropy and Gini coefficients need to be calculated and displayed to quantify the distribution characteristics.

3.1.2 Proposed Approach

To address the challenges above, we developed the following approach, with specific solutions mapped to each challenge:

- **To address computational complexity**, we use a **discrete-time simulation model** with efficient data structures optimised for tracking intervals and relation statistics. The simulation is implemented in Python with vectorised operations where possible to handle many events in parallel. For expensive computations, results are cached to avoid redundant calculation.
- **To ensure full coverage**, we employ two strategies: (1) running very large simulations (tens of millions of trials) for key parameter settings, ensuring even rare relations are observed enough times for stable estimates; and (2) storing these pre-computed results in a structured format (JSON files) that can be quickly loaded for analysis or display, without requiring re-simulation.
- **To handle temporal dependencies in composition**, we design a simulation process that generates all three intervals (A, B, C) within a single timeline execution. We label them strictly by order of appearance to maintain consistency and collect

statistics only when all three intervals have completed, ensuring the relation triple (R_1, R_2, R_3) reflects the true process dynamics.

- **To balance interactivity and accuracy**, we implement a two-tier approach: (1) pre-compute and cache results for a grid of representative (p, q) values for instant access; and (2) provide on-demand simulation with a smaller but still reasonable number of trials (e.g., 100,000) for exploratory analysis of arbitrary parameter combinations. This gives users immediate feedback while still maintaining acceptable accuracy for exploration.
- **To address visualisation challenges**, we develop an interactive Dash application with multiple coordinated views: bar charts for relation distributions, conditional distribution displays for chosen relation pairs, and heat maps for the full composition matrix. Relations are grouped by type (e.g., pairing each relation with its converse) using consistent colour coding, and users can filter or focus on specific relations. Summary statistics (entropy, Gini, divergence) provide quantitative measures to complement the visual display.

At a high level, our approach uses:

- A discrete-time simulation model where:
 - With probability p , a new interval is spawned (born) at each time step
 - Every active interval independently survives to the next step with probability $(1 - q)$, or ends (dies) with probability q
- A Monte Carlo engine that runs this simulation repeatedly to collect relation and composition statistics
- A data storage layer for caching results of expensive computations
- A web-based user interface for interactive exploration and visualisation

3.2 Overview of the Design

The system is organised with a clear separation between the **back-end simulation logic** and the **front-end visualisation logic**. The main components are:

1. **Monte Carlo Engine (Back-end)**: A Python module that generates intervals for given (p, q) and collects statistics. It exposes functions like `simulate_relations(p, q, N)` and `simulate_compositions(p, q, N)`. Internally it handles random number generation and interval bookkeeping.

2. **Data Storage:** Results for key scenarios are cached in simple JSON files such as `sim_results.json` and `comp_results.json`, keyed by (p, q) .
3. **Dash Application (Front-end):** Built with Plotly Dash. User actions (slider changes, button clicks) trigger callbacks that either fetch pre-computed data or invoke the Monte Carlo engine. The front-end renders bar charts, heat-maps and summary statistics, using colour coding to group converse relations for clarity.

Figure 3.1: System architecture showing the relationship between the four main components: user interface for parameter input, simulation engine for interval generation and relation detection, data storage for persisting results, and visualisation components for displaying analysis outcomes.

Figure 3.1 illustrates how the user interacts with the front-end, which in turn invokes computations or retrieves stored data from the back-end, and how results flow back for visualisation. The design emphasises modularity: the simulation engine can be run independently of the web UI, and the UI is largely agnostic to how data are produced. This separation allows for extensive offline analysis while still supporting interactive exploration.

In terms of data model, each Allen relation is identified by its symbol; we maintain mappings to human-readable names and an index (0–12) for array storage. Converse relation pairs (e.g., *before* — *after*, *meets* — *met-by*, *overlaps* — *overlapped-by*) are consistently grouped in both storage and visualisation to highlight symmetries. Composition outcomes are stored as a $13 \times 13 \times 13$ array or an equivalent dictionary keyed by (R_1, R_2) with a distribution over R_3 .

We also considered performance and usability in the design: by pre-running simulations for common scenarios and keeping all computation in Python on the server side, the app can quickly load results without burdening the user’s browser. This also avoids potential security concerns related to running complex computational code in the browser environment. Dash’s reactive model ensures that when a user adjusts a parameter, only the necessary parts of the display are recomputed, further improving responsiveness.

3.3 Summary

This chapter defined the research problem as quantifying the prior probabilities of Allen’s interval relations under a probabilistic model and extending that to relation composition. We identified key challenges including computational complexity, ensuring coverage of rare relations, handling temporal dependencies, balancing interactivity with accuracy, and effective visualisation. Our design addresses these challenges through a modular architecture that combines efficient Monte Carlo simulation with interactive visualisation, enabling both rigorous offline analysis and exploratory, user-driven experimentation. The simulation engine generates interval data according to the birth-death model parameters, while the web interface allows users to explore the resulting distributions through various visualisations and metrics. In the next chapter we delve into implementation details, describing how this design was realised in code and what practical decisions were made to ensure efficiency and correctness.

Chapter 4

Implementation

Building upon the design outlined earlier, the implementation phase involved (i) developing the simulation engine, (ii) running large-scale simulations to gather empirical data, and (iii) building a Dash web application for visualisation and interactive exploration. This chapter details the principal implementation choices, including data structures, algorithms, and the optimisations adopted to handle up to ten million trials per scenario.

All code and associated resources described in this chapter are publicly available in the project repository at github.com/vxrdis/allen-interval-probabilities, allowing for reproduction of results and further experimentation.

4.1 Simulation engine

The simulator is written in **Python 3.9.6**. Although Python is not the fastest language for tight loops, its rich ecosystem — especially **NumPy** — and the ease of multiprocessing parallelism outweighed that drawback. By combining vectorised operations with a modest amount of process-level parallelism, we obtained throughputs of several million triple trials per minute on commodity hardware.

4.1.1 Module structure

The project’s codebase is organised into modules corresponding to different functional units:

`constants.py` Core definitions of Allen interval relations, symbolic representation mappings, relation colours, and reference probability distributions

`reference_tables.py` Predefined composition tables and theoretical reference data presented as HTML for the web interface

`intervals.py` Fundamental interval generation algorithms and relation detection functions implementing the birth-death state machine

`relations.py` Mathematical representation of Allen relations with symbolic encoding and composition operations like superposition

`stats.py` Statistical analysis utilities implementing entropy, Gini coefficient, Jensen-Shannon divergence and other information-theoretic metrics

`simulations.py` Primary simulation engine coordinating interval pair generation, relation detection, and result tallying

`comp_runner.py` Extended framework for generating triple intervals and building composition tables with relation probability distributions

`batch_runner.py` Command-line interface for systematic parameter-space exploration and batch processing with progress tracking

`sim_results.py` Utilities for formatting numerical results and generating human-readable reports from simulation data

`comp_results.py` Processors for composition results, including fraction conversion, statistical summarisation, and report generation

`app.py` Interactive Dash web application providing visualisation tools, callbacks, and user interface components

This modular design promotes separation of concerns, allowing the simulation engine to operate independently of the web interface. This enables both offline batch processing and interactive use through the dashboard.

4.1.2 Interval-generation algorithm

The interval generation process follows a memoryless birth-death model: at each discrete time step, new intervals may be born with probability p , and each existing interval may die with probability q . The memoryless property means the probability of an interval ending has no relation to how long it has already been active; each interval's fate is determined independently at each time step.

Listing 1 shows a simplified version of the discrete-time birth–death algorithm. The loop continues until at least three intervals have terminated, at which point the first three (ordered by start time) are returned as A, B, C .

Listing 1: Single-timeline simulation (simplified for clarity)

```

1 from random import random
2
3 def simulate_one_timeline(p_born: float, p_die: float):
4     # Return a list of three finished intervals (start, end),
5     # sorted by start time.
6
7     active, finished, t = [], [], 0
8     # active intervals as (start, end); end=None if ongoing
9     while len(finished) < 3:
10        # Possible birth at current time tick
11        if random() < p_born:
12            # a new interval starts at time t
13            active.append([t, None])
14
15        # Possible deaths at current tick
16        for interval in active:
17            if random() < p_die and interval[1] is None:
18                interval[1] = t
19                finished.append(tuple(interval))
20        # Remove intervals that have finished
21        active = [iv for iv in active if iv[1] is None]
22        t += 1
23
24        # Keep the first three finished intervals
25        # (earliest start, tie-break by shorter duration)
26        finished.sort(key=lambda iv: (iv[0], iv[1] - iv[0]))
27        return finished[:3]

```

Key points:

- Only one new interval *may* start in a given tick (one Bernoulli trial with parameter p_{born}).
- Several intervals can terminate in the same tick; if two share a boundary exactly, relations such as *meets* or *equals* legitimately arise. Because the simulation is discrete, such coincidences have positive probability.
- Extreme parameter settings ($p_{\text{born}} = q_{\text{die}} \ll 1$) lead to long runtimes per triple. This is addressed in Section 4.1.4.

Determining Allen relations. Given two intervals (s_1, e_1) and (s_2, e_2) with $s_1 \leq s_2$, the helper in Listing 2 returns the Allen symbol. All 13 cases are covered (both orientations); only representative clauses are shown below.

Listing 2: Allen relation helper (abridged)

```

1  def allen_relation(iv1, iv2):
2      (s1, e1), (s2, e2) = iv1, iv2
3      if s1 > s2:                # normalise orientation
4          return converse[allen_relation(iv2, iv1)]
5
6      if e1 < s2:                return 'p'          # precedes
7      if e1 == s2:              return 'm'          # meets
8      if s1 == s2 and e1 == e2: return 'e'          # equals
9
10     if s1 == s2 and e1 < e2:   return 's'          # starts
11
12     if s1 < s2 < e1 < e2:     return 'o'          # overlaps
13
14     if s1 < s2 and e1 > e2:    return 'D'          # contains
15
16     if e1 == e2 and s1 < s2:   return 'F'          # finished by
17
18     if e1 == e2 and s1 > s2:   return 'f'          # finishes
19
20     # ...remaining tests for d/D and converses...

```

The dict `converse` maps each symbol to its converse (e.g. `'p'↔'P'`).

4.1.3 Composition analysis

For composition analysis — where we consider three intervals A , B , C with relations $R_1 = (A, R_1, B)$ and $R_2 = (B, R_2, C)$ composing to resultant relation $R_3 = (A, R_3, C)$ — we extend the pairwise simulation approach. The module `comp_runner.py` handles this task.

It's crucial to note that for composition analysis, all three intervals must be generated within a single timeline execution. Independently generating pairs (A, B) and (B, C) would not correctly model the temporal dependencies that arise when B serves as the “bridge” between A and C . Our simulation ensures that triples properly reflect the underlying stochastic process, labelling intervals strictly by order of appearance to maintain consistency.

The procedure for generating empirical composition data is:

For each simulation trial (up to N trials):

Simulate three intervals A, B, C until all dead;

Derive $R_1 = \text{rel}(A, B)$, $R_2 = \text{rel}(B, C)$, $R_3 = \text{rel}(A, C)$;

if R_1, R_2, R_3 are all valid: **record** an instance of $(R_1, R_2 \rightarrow R_3)$.

In rare cases where relation detection fails (which should not happen with correct simulation logic), the triple is discarded. This yields an empirical probability distribution $P(R_3 | R_1, R_2)$ for the composition $R_1 \circ R_2$. With sufficient trials (millions), every one of the 169 possible ordered pairs (R_1, R_2) is observed at least once for moderate parameter values, confirming that the simulation provides broad coverage.

In extreme cases (very low birth and death probabilities), a few rare combinations involving the “equals” relation may not be witnessed, as these specific configurations have vanishingly small probability. This limitation is discussed further in the evaluation chapter.

4.1.4 Data structures and optimisation

- **Counters.** Single-relation counts use a length-13 NumPy vector. Composition counts use a dense $13^3 = 2197$ integer cube; its memory footprint is negligible.
- **Vectorised deaths.** For each tick we draw $|\text{active}|$ uniform random numbers in a single NumPy call and compare them with q_{die} , replacing the inner Python loop.
- **Parallelism.** Large runs are split across CPU cores with `multiprocessing.Pool`. Each worker writes its local counts to `numpy.memmap`, after which the parent aggregates the partial arrays.

With these optimisations, 10^7 triple trials at $(p, q) = (0.1, 0.1)$ execute in about eight minutes on a 12-core desktop; the sparsest case $(0.01, 0.01)$ requires roughly forty minutes.

4.1.5 Memory management

Given the scale of simulation (up to tens of millions of iterations), careful memory management is crucial. The implementation avoids storing full state histories; instead, it records only the final relations or the last transitions needed for counting frequencies. When a trial yields a triple (R_1, R_2, R_3) , it immediately updates the count in the composition table and discards the full history.

The memory footprint is thus dominated by the table of counts (a fixed-size 13×13 matrix for composition counts plus overhead for mapping percentages) and a running tally of global relation frequencies. This approach allows even 10^7 trials to be executed sequentially without memory exhaustion, trading off computation time for memory efficiency.

4.1.6 Validation and quality assurance

Several validation strategies were employed to ensure the correctness of the implementation:

1. **Deterministic extremes.** Setting $(p, q) = (1, 1)$ yields runs in which every interval lasts exactly one tick. As expected, *meets* and its converse dominate; other relations appear only through tie-breaking. The simulated frequencies matched hand calculations.
2. **Symmetry.** For (p, q) pairs with $p = q$, empirical counts of converse relations $(p/P, d/D, \dots)$ were equal to machine precision. This property follows from the symmetry of the generation process and serves as a powerful correctness check.
3. **Baseline checks.** The $(0.5, 0.5)$ scenario reproduced exactly the Suliman 7-vs-6 distribution (JS divergence $< 10^{-4}$), providing external validation.
4. **Marginals.** Summing R_3 over R_2 and R_1 in the composition cube recovers the pairwise distribution, providing an internal consistency check.
5. **Distribution normalisation.** All probability distributions summed to 1.0 (within floating-point error), confirming proper normalisation.

These validations build confidence in the implementation’s correctness and the reliability of the results.

4.2 Determinism and reproducibility

Given the stochastic nature of the simulations, we implemented mechanisms to ensure reproducibility. The Python random number generator is seeded using `random.seed(value)` to produce a deterministic sequence of pseudorandom numbers.

In the simulation modules, an option is provided (via command-line arguments or constants) to set a specific seed before running trials. For example:

```
run(p_born=0.1, p_die=0.1, trials=1000000, seed=42)
```

Two runs with identical seeds and parameters generate the exact same sequence of interval lifetimes, ensuring reproducible outcomes. This determinism was verified during development and proved valuable when testing changes to the relation-mapping logic.

For the web application, which is typically stateless between sessions, we seed the random generator at the start of each simulation with a value derived from the input parameters. This approach ensures consistent results when a user repeatedly requests a simulation with the same parameters.

All random decisions in the simulation (births and deaths of intervals) stem from Python’s `random` module, so seeding it controls the entire simulation process deterministically. The implementation contains no other sources of nondeterminism; it does not rely on system time, parallel threads, or hardware-based randomness.

4.3 Metric computation

Entropy (base 2) and the Gini index are computed directly from the empirical probabilities $\{p_i\}_{i=1}^{13}$. The Jensen–Shannon divergence is evaluated relative to three reference distributions: the uniform distribution, the Suliman distribution (0.5, 0.5), and an empirical Fernando–Vogel proxy derived from (0.01, 0.01). Zero probabilities are treated according to the standard convention, where $0 \log_2 0$ is defined to be zero.

The module `stats.py` provides functions to calculate these metrics. An example implementation is presented in Listing 3.

Listing 3: Entropy and Gini coefficient computation

```
1  import math
2
3  def entropy(counts):
4      total = sum(counts.values())
5      if total == 0:
6          return 0.0
7      # Convert counts to probability fractions
8      probs = [count / total
9               for count in counts.values() if count > 0]
10     # Shannon entropy (bits)
11     return -sum(p * math.log2(p) for p in probs)
12
13  def gini(counts):
14     values = list(counts.values())
15     if sum(values) == 0:
16         return 0.0
17     total = sum(values)
18     # Gini index = 1 - sum(p_i^2) for all relations i
19     return 1.0 - sum((count/total) ** 2 for count in values)
```

The Gini coefficient measures inequality or concentration in the distribution, computed as $G = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^{13} p_i^2$. For a uniform distribution, this gives the maximum $G = 1 - 13 \cdot (1/13)^2$.

When computing JS divergence, we identify which reference model has the smallest value and label it as the “best fit” model for the given parameter regime.

4.4 Web application front-end

The Dash application follows the standard pattern: a single `app.py` initialises a ‘`dc.Tabs`’ container whose three tabs correspond to the main experimental tasks.

Probabilities of Allen Interval Relations

Relation Simulation

[Composition Analysis](#) [Matrix Analysis](#)

Simulation Parameters

Birth Probability (pBorn): 0.01

Death Probability (pDie): 0.01

Use input fields for precise values (e.g. 0.001)

Number of Trials:

Run Simulation

Export Results as CSV

Export Results as JSON

Simulation History

Latest simulation: p=0.01, q=0.01
 Best fit: F-V
 Total runs: 7
 Last run: None

Model Fit Analysis:

Best Fit: F-V (JS = 0.0188)

Compared to:

- Uniform: 0.2202
- Fernando-Vogel: 0.0188
- Suliman: 0.2684

Relation Distribution

Show reference models: Uniform Fernando-Vogel Suliman Sort relations by frequency

Allen Relation Distribution (p=0.01, q=0.01, n=10000000)

Mode: **After (0.247)**

Export as PNG

Entropy	Gini Coefficient	Std Dev	Best Fit
2.5962	0.6043	904056.2545	F-V JS = 0.0188

JS (Uniform)	JS (F-V)	JS (Suliman)
0.2202	0.0188	0.2684

Entropy Heatmap

Heat map shows entropy across parameter space

Max denominator for fraction display:

Higher values give more precise fractions but may be harder to read

Load Previous Results

Upload previously saved JSON results:

Drag and Drop or Select File

Files should be named sim_p[value]_q[value].json

Relation Distribution

Show reference models: Uniform Fernando-Vogel Suliman Sort relations by frequency

Allen Relation Distribution (p=0.01, q=0.01, n=10000000)

Mode: **After (0.247)**

Export as PNG

Entropy	Gini Coefficient	Std Dev	Best Fit
2.5962	0.6043	904056.2545	F-V JS = 0.0188

JS (Uniform)	JS (F-V)	JS (Suliman)
0.2202	0.0188	0.2684

Metrics History

Metrics Over Simulation Runs

Detailed Results

Relation	Name	Count	Probability	= Fraction
p	Before	2474789	0.2475	1/4
m	Meets	24911	0.0025	0
o	Overlaps	1230890	0.1231	1/8
F	Finished By	12545	0.0013	0
D	Contains	1232818	0.1233	1/8
s	Starts	24901	0.0025	0
e	Equals	287	0.0000	0
S	Started By	25018	0.0025	0
d	During	1233454	0.1233	1/8
f	Finishes	12528	0.0013	0
O	Overlapped By	1228339	0.1228	1/8
M	Met By	24664	0.0025	0
P	After	2474856	0.2475	1/4

Figure 4.1: Screenshot of the interactive Dash application showing the relation simulation tab with parameter controls, distribution visualisation, and statistical metrics.

4.4.1 Layout and interactivity

The application is structured into three primary tabs, each handling a different aspect of the analysis:

Relation simulation Allows users to specify birth probability p , death probability q , and number of trials N using sliders and numeric inputs. Upon clicking “Run Simulation”, the app displays a bar chart showing frequencies of all 13 Allen relations, along with metrics (entropy, Gini) and identification of the closest reference distribution.

Composition analysis Users select two relations R_1 and R_2 from dropdown menus, along with p and q values. The app then displays a bar chart showing the probability distribution of the resulting relation R_3 , highlighting which outcomes are most likely when those two relations compose.

Matrix analysis Provides a holistic view by displaying a 13×13 heatmap matrix where each cell represents either the entropy or the most likely outcome (mode) for a given (R_1, R_2) pair. Users can switch between different pre-computed (p, q) scenarios and toggle between entropy and mode visualisation.

The interface employs consistent colour-coding throughout: converse relation pairs share similar colours (e.g., *before* and *after* might both be shades of blue), making it easier to identify patterns visually. Tooltips provide additional information when users hover over chart elements.

4.4.2 Interactive simulation approach

Since running a full 10^7 trial simulation interactively would be impractical, the implementation uses a two-tier approach:

1. For demonstration purposes, the app runs a smaller number of trials (e.g., 10,000) when parameters change, giving a quick but approximate estimate of the distribution.
2. The app can load cached or pre-computed results for key parameter points, where exhaustive 10-million trial results were generated offline.

The app informs users when they are viewing approximate results versus high-precision pre-computed data. For arbitrary (p, q) values not in the pre-computed set, the app runs a smaller simulation on the fly, warning users about the higher variance in these estimates compared to the full simulations.

Listing 4 shows a simplified callback that handles the simulation request:

Listing 4: Dash callback for simulation results

```

1 @app.callback(
2     Output("simulation-results", "data"),
3     Input("run-button", "n_clicks"),
4     State("p-born-input", "value"),
5     State("p-die-input", "value"),
6     State("trials-input", "value"),
7     prevent_initial_call=True,
8 )
9 def run_simulation(n_clicks, p_born, p_die, trials):
10     if n_clicks is None:
11         # no action if button not clicked
12         return {}, dash.no_update, dash.no_update
13
14     # Run Monte Carlo simulation for given parameters
15     # raw frequency of each relation
16     counts = arSimulate(p_born, p_die, trials)
17     total = sum(counts.values())
18
19     # Calculate distribution
20     distribution = {
21         rel: count/total
22         for rel, count in counts.items() if total > 0
23     }
24
25     # Compare to reference models via Jensen--Shannon divergence
26     js_uniform = js_divergence(distribution, UNIFORM_DISTRIBUTION)
27     js_fv = js_divergence(
28         distribution, FERNANDO_VOGEL_DISTRIBUTION)
29     js_suliman = js_divergence(distribution, SULIMAN_DISTRIBUTION)
30
31     # Determine best fitting model
32     best_model = (
33         "Uniform" if (js_uniform <= js_fv and
34                     js_uniform <= js_suliman)
35         else "Fernando-Vogel" if js_fv <= js_suliman
36         else "Suliman"
37     )
38
39     # Package results (distribution, raw counts, and summary stats)
40     time_str = datetime.now().strftime("%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S")
41     results = {
42         "distribution": distribution,
43         "raw_counts": counts,

```

```

44         "stats": {
45             "best_fit": best_model,
46             "timestamp": time_str
47         },
48     }
49     return results, dash.no_update, results["stats"]["timestamp"]

```

This design balances interactivity and accuracy: users can explore the parameter space freely with instant feedback, while also accessing high-fidelity results for specific scenarios without waiting for lengthy computations.

4.5 Deployment

4.5.1 Deployment on Render

To ensure consistent availability of the application, we deployed it on the Render platform, which offers a straightforward deployment pipeline for Python web applications. Render integrates directly with GitHub, eliminating the need for containerisation while still providing a reliable hosting environment.

The application is configured on Render with the following settings:

- **Build Command:** `pip install -r requirements.txt`
- **Start Command:** `gunicorn app:server`
- **Instance Type:** Free tier (suitable for demonstration purposes)
- **Auto-Deploy:** Enabled for continuous integration from the GitHub repository
- **Health Check Path:** `/`

This configuration ensures that when changes are pushed to the main branch on GitHub, Render automatically rebuilds and deploys the updated application. The service is publicly accessible at allen-interval.onrender.com, allowing users to interact with the simulation and analysis tools without needing to install anything locally.

The deployment approach balances simplicity with reliability, avoiding unnecessary complexity while ensuring the application remains accessible throughout the project lifecycle. This direct GitHub-to-Render pipeline streamlined both development and demonstration workflows.

4.6 Results data

Seven scenarios were simulated at $N = 10\,000\,000$ triple trials each:

$$(p, q) \in \{(0.01, 0.01), (0.01, 0.1), (0.1, 0.01), (0.1, 0.1), (0.1, 0.2), (0.2, 0.1), (0.5, 0.5)\}.$$

For composition analysis, we tracked all possible relation triplets (R_1, R_2, R_3) . The following snippet demonstrates how we constructed the probabilistic composition matrix:

Listing 5: Composition matrix construction

```
1 # Initialise composition count table for all 13*13 relation pairs
2 composition_counts = {
3     r1: {r2: {} for r2 in ALLEN_RELATIONS}
4     for r1 in ALLEN_RELATIONS
5 }
6
7 # Aggregate outcomes from many triple simulations
8 # (runs is a list of (R1, R2, R3) tuples)
9 for (r1, r2, r3) in runs:
10     comp_table = composition_counts[r1][r2]
11     comp_table[r3] = comp_table.get(r3, 0) + 1
12
13 # (Later, these counts are normalised to probabilities
14 # for each (r1, r2) pair)
```

Table 5.1 (p.29) summarises the global metrics. Detailed distributions and full composition cubes are archived in the accompanying data directory and are accessible through the Dash interface.

4.7 Codebase Metrics

The public repository consists of approximately 6040 non-blank, non-comment lines of Python distributed across 11 source files¹. The `app.py` module alone constitutes over 4400 lines. Precomputed JSON fixtures for the Dash interface collectively occupy around 300 kB of disk space.

4.8 Challenges and solutions

During implementation, several technical challenges were encountered:

¹Measured using `find`, `grep`, and `wc -l`, excluding virtual-environment and `.git` artefacts.

- **Slow sparse regimes.** Scenarios with $p, q < 0.01$ were deemed out of scope after preliminary timing runs. At extremely low probabilities, the simulation becomes prohibitively slow as intervals rarely start or end. Furthermore, these edge cases offer diminishing analytical value, as they predominantly produce before/after relations with minimal overlap.
- **Tie-breaking bias.** When two intervals share a start time, the A-B-C labelling becomes arbitrary. We addressed this by recognising that while individual timeline events might be labelled differently depending on tie-breaking rules, the overall distribution of relations remains unaffected. Essentially, the simulation is symmetric with respect to swapping interval identities, ensuring that frequencies remain correct regardless of the labelling choice.
- **Data consistency.** To eliminate discrepancies between the simulation scripts and the Dash app, the JSON files store final probabilities rather than raw counts. This design decision prevents any inconsistencies that might arise from re-normalising or recalculating percentages in different parts of the system. The app performs no recomputation of the fundamental distributions, ensuring what users see is exactly what was simulated.
- **Batch automation.** The need to run multiple lengthy simulations (10^7 trials for each of seven scenarios) required automation. We developed `batch_runner.py`, which managed sequentially running simulations with different parameters, saving results incrementally, and handling unexpected interruptions gracefully through checkpointing.

The implementation thus delivers both an efficient simulator and an interactive exploratory tool, forming the basis for the evaluation presented in Chapter 5.

Chapter 5

Evaluation

This chapter evaluates the simulation experiments, concentrating on the empirical probabilities of Allen relations under varying birth–death parameters and on the probabilistic composition of those relations. The discussion is organised into four sections:

1. experimental methodology, describing our approach to data collection and validation;
2. the single–pair relation distributions for several representative (p, q) settings; ¹
3. probabilistic composition examples with analysis of emergent patterns; and
4. convergence and reliability analyses, including variance estimates for low-probability events.

Where possible, we compare the empirical figures with theoretical expectations from the literature so as to validate and contextualise our findings.

5.1 Experimental methodology

For the evaluation, we selected a representative set of birth–death probability pairs spanning the parameter space from sparse to dense timelines. Seven (p, q) configurations were thoroughly examined, each with 10^7 independent trials:

- $(0.01, 0.01)$ – very low birth and death rates (sparse, long-lived intervals)
- $(0.01, 0.10)$ – low birth, higher death (sparse, short-lived intervals)
- $(0.10, 0.01)$ – higher birth, low death (many overlapping intervals)
- $(0.10, 0.10)$ – moderate birth and death (balanced regime)

¹Throughout, p denotes the birth probability and q the death probability per time-step.

- (0.10, 0.20) – moderate birth, higher death (moderately sparse)
- (0.20, 0.10) – higher birth, moderate death (moderately dense)
- (0.50, 0.50) – very high birth and death (dense, high-churn regime)

These scenarios were chosen to systematically sample the parameter space by varying p and q in increments of 0.1 (except for the extreme cases), providing insight into how relation probabilities change across different temporal regimes. The (0.50, 0.50) case was specifically included as it represents the high-churn extreme that matches Suliman’s theoretical predictions (Suliman, 2021).

For each scenario, we performed two types of simulations with discrete time steps:

1. **Relation simulations:** Each trial generated a pair of intervals and recorded their Allen relation. This yielded the empirical distribution $P(R)$ for each of the 13 relations.
2. **Composition simulations:** Each trial generated three intervals (A, B, C) within a single timeline and recorded the three relations (R_1, R_2, R_3) between them. This required separate dedicated simulation runs to ensure proper temporal dependencies between all three intervals.

The large number of trials (10^7 per scenario) ensures that even rare relations (such as *equals*, with probability often below 10^{-4}) are observed sufficiently often to estimate probabilities with high confidence. With this sample size, standard errors for events with probability p are approximately $\sqrt{p(1-p)/N}$, which for even the rarest relations translates to relative errors of up to about 7%.

During analysis, we verified the consistency of the results against several invariants. For scenarios with $p = q$, frequency counts of converse relations (e.g., *before/after*) were equal to within statistical error, confirming the simulation’s symmetry. Similarly, for each simulation we confirmed that the total probability mass summed to 1.0 as expected.

5.2 Relation distributions

Table 5.1 summarises key aggregate statistics for all seven scenarios, and the following figures offer visual representations of the distributions for all parameter settings.

Table 5.1: Summary statistics for the relation distributions (10^7 samples per scenario). **Mode** indicates the most frequent relation; **Entropy** (bits) quantifies uncertainty; **Gini** measures inequality (0 uniform, 1 degenerate); **Best fit** shows the reference model with minimal Jensen–Shannon divergence: Uniform (**U**), Fernando–Vogel (**F–V**), or Suliman’s memory-less model (**S**).

p	q	Entropy	Gini	Mode	Meaning	Best fit (JS)
0.01	0.01	2.596	0.604	P	<i>After</i>	F–V (0.019)
0.01	0.10	1.632	0.789	p	<i>Before</i>	F–V (0.208)
0.10	0.01	2.655	0.600	D	<i>Contains</i>	F–V (0.071)
0.10	0.10	3.048	0.501	p	<i>Before</i>	F–V (0.061)
0.10	0.20	2.830	0.558	P	<i>After</i>	F–V (0.125)
0.20	0.10	3.307	0.375	o	<i>Overlaps</i>	U (0.075)
0.50	0.50	3.522	0.240	M	<i>Met-by</i>	S (< 0.01)

5.2.1 Distribution characteristics across regimes

The observed trends across different (p, q) regimes reveal patterns that align with intuitive expectations about interval dynamics. Key observations from these distributions include:

- **Sparse timelines** ($p \ll q$) are dominated by sequential relations. For $(0.01, 0.10)$, *before/after* jointly exceed 90%, entropy falls to 1.63 bits, and the Gini coefficient approaches 0.79.
- **Dense timelines** ($p \gg q$) favour overlap and nesting. For $(0.10, 0.01)$ all four overlap/contain variants (*overlaps, overlapped-by, during, contains*) occur with nearly equal frequency (approximately 21–21.4% each) and together account for roughly 85%.
- **Balanced settings** (e.g. $(0.10, 0.10)$) yield a much flatter distribution: *before/after* are approximately 22% each; the four overlap/contains variants are around 8–12% each; boundary relations like *meets* and *met-by* are about 2–3% each; while relations like *equals* occur as rarely as 0.3%. The entropy surpasses 3 bits, and the profile matches the Fernando–Vogel prior (Fernando & Vogel, 2019).

We now examine each of these regimes in more detail, following the progression shown in the figures.

In the **sparse regime with long-lived intervals** $(0.01, 0.01)$, shown in Figure 5.1, we observe a dominance of *before* and *after* relations at approximately 25% each, with four containment/overlap relations jointly comprising nearly 50% of all cases. This represents a moderately skewed distribution with relatively low entropy.

Allen Relation Distribution ($p=0.01, q=0.01, n=10000000$)

Figure 5.1: Distribution of the 13 Allen interval relations in the sparse regime with long-lived intervals ($p = 0.01, q = 0.01$), based on 10^7 trials. The distribution shows *before* and *after* relations dominating at approximately 25% each, with other relations occurring less frequently.

In the **sparse sequential regime** (0.01,0.10), shown in Figure 5.2, intervals are born rarely and die quickly. With few intervals alive simultaneously, the process tends to produce one interval at a time with long gaps between them. As expected, *before* and *after* relations dominate at approximately 45.2% each, accounting for over 90% of all relations. The remaining relations — mostly those implying some overlap — occur rarely. For instance, *overlaps/overlapped-by* and *contains/during* each appear in only about 2% of cases. Relations requiring precise endpoint alignment are exceptionally rare: *meets/met-by* occur with frequency $\approx 0.4\%$, while *equals* appears in a mere 0.03% of interval pairs.

The **balanced regime** (0.10, 0.10), shown in Figure 5.3, exhibits a much more uniform distribution. While *before* and *after* remain the most common relations at approximately 22% each, other relations gain prominence, with overlap and containment relations occurring at 8–12% frequency.

In the **dense timeline regime** (0.10,0.01), shown in Figure 5.4, the dynamics shift dramatically. With many long-lived intervals, containment and nesting relations dominate.

Allen Relation Distribution ($p=0.01, q=0.10, n=10000000$)

Figure 5.2: Distribution of the 13 Allen interval relations in the sparse regime with short-lived intervals ($p = 0.01, q = 0.10$). The distribution is highly skewed, with *before* and *after* relations dominating at approximately 45% each, while the remaining relations have much lower probabilities.

All four overlap/contain variants (overlaps, overlapped-by, during, contains) together account for over 85% of all relations, with sequential relations becoming relatively rare.

The **moderately dense** (0.20, 0.10) and **moderately sparse** (0.10, 0.20) regimes, shown in Figures 5.5 and 5.6 respectively, represent intermediate cases with characteristics that blend the extremes.

Finally, in the **dense high-churn regime** (0.50, 0.50), shown in Figure 5.7, the pattern transforms dramatically. With intervals constantly starting and ending, many overlap by chance, and endpoint coincidences become common. The resulting distribution approaches uniformity, though with interesting biases. The most frequent relation is *equals* at approximately 11.1%, closely followed by *meets*, *met-by*, *starts*, *started-by*, *before*, and *after*, each also around 11%. Together, these seven relations account for about 77% of all cases. The remaining six relations — those involving proper overlaps — each occur approximately 3.7% of the time.

This pattern reveals a counterintuitive property: in high-churn regimes, intervals are more likely to coincide exactly at endpoints than to exhibit partial overlaps. This stems from the memoryless nature of the process, where the probability of an interval ending

Allen Relation Distribution ($p=0.10, q=0.10, n=10000000$)

Figure 5.3: Distribution of the 13 Allen interval relations in the balanced regime ($p = 0.10, q = 0.10$). The distribution is more uniform, with *before* and *after* relations at approximately 22% each, overlap and containment relations at 8–12% each, boundary relations like *meets* and *met-by* at 2–3%, and *equals* appearing quite rarely at approximately 0.3%.

exactly when another starts or ends becomes significant when there are many short-lived intervals.

5.2.2 Entropy and distribution diversity

To quantify the diversity of relation distributions, we use Shannon entropy (in bits) and the Gini coefficient. Entropy measures uncertainty — higher values indicate more uniform distributions where predicting the relation between random intervals becomes difficult. The Gini coefficient measures inequality — values closer to 1 indicate highly skewed distributions dominated by few relations.

Figure 5.8 depicts entropy values across the (p, q) parameter space, revealing a clear pattern:

The entropy pattern reveals a diagonal ridge of high values when $p \approx q$ (especially at larger values), and valleys when $p \ll q$ or $p \gg q$. In the sparse regime $(0.01, 0.10)$, entropy reaches only 1.63 bits — far below the maximum $\log_2 13 \approx 3.70$ bits — reflecting high

Figure 5.4: Distribution of the 13 Allen interval relations in the dense timeline regime ($p = 0.10, q = 0.01$). With many long-lived intervals, overlap and nesting relations dominate. All four overlap/contain variants (overlaps, overlapped-by, during, contains) occur with nearly identical frequencies of approximately 21–21.4% each and together account for over 85% of all relations, with sequential relations becoming relatively rare.

predictability. The corresponding Gini coefficient of 0.789 confirms extreme inequality in this distribution. By contrast, the dense regime (0.50, 0.50) achieves entropy of 3.52 bits with Gini coefficient 0.240, indicating an almost uniform distribution.

The general trend when holding one probability fixed and varying the other resembles a concave pattern. For example, with $p = 0.1$ fixed and q varying through $\{0.01, 0.1, 0.2\}$, the respective entropies are $\{2.656, 3.048, 2.830\}$ bits — highest in the balanced case. Similarly, with $q = 0.1$ fixed and p varying through $\{0.01, 0.1, 0.2\}$, entropies are $\{1.632, 3.048, 3.307\}$ bits — showing increasing uncertainty as interval density rises.

From a practical standpoint, these entropy measurements have significant implications for temporal reasoning systems. In low-entropy regimes (like sparse timelines), systems might safely assume that intervals are typically sequential, simplifying reasoning. In high-entropy regimes, however, all relations become sufficiently probable that none can be ignored without sacrificing accuracy.

Figure 5.5: Distribution of the 13 Allen interval relations in the moderately dense regime ($p = 0.20, q = 0.10$). The distribution becomes more balanced, with *contains* as the modal relation (13.55%, marginally above *overlaps* at 13.54%) and a more even spread across different relation types.

5.2.3 Comparison with theoretical models

We compared our empirical distributions with three theoretical models using Jensen–Shannon (JS) divergence, a symmetric measure of difference between probability distributions:

- **Uniform model:** Assumes all 13 relations are equally likely ($1/13$ probability each)
- **Fernando–Vogel model:** A non-uniform distribution based on classifying intervals by duration (Fernando & Vogel, 2019)
- **Suliman’s model:** A memory-less model assuming independence between interval start and end times (Suliman, 2021)

The JS divergence measures reveal clear patterns:

- For sparse scenarios (e.g., $(0.01, 0.01)$, $(0.01, 0.10)$), the Fernando–Vogel model provides an excellent fit (JS divergence as low as 0.019). This confirms that the F–V model accurately captures the distribution in regimes with limited interval overlap.

Allen Relation Distribution ($p=0.10, q=0.20, n=10000000$)

Figure 5.6: Distribution of the 13 Allen interval relations in the moderately sparse regime ($p = 0.10, q = 0.20$). Sequential relations (*before* and *after*) remain strong at about 30% each, overlap and containment relations each appear at approximately 6%, and boundary relations like *meets* and *met-by* occur at about 3.4% each.

- For intermediate balanced scenarios (e.g., $(0.10, 0.10)$), F–V remains the best fit ($JS \approx 0.061$), though both Uniform ($JS \approx 0.119$) and Suliman ($JS \approx 0.153$) also provide reasonable approximations.
- For the moderately dense case $(0.20, 0.10)$, the Uniform model slightly outperforms F–V ($JS \approx 0.075$ vs 0.077), with Suliman’s model showing higher divergence ($JS \approx 0.128$), suggesting the distribution flattens considerably at higher birth rates.
- For the high-churn case $(0.50, 0.50)$, Suliman’s model matches our empirical results nearly perfectly ($JS < 0.01$). This striking confirmation validates Suliman’s analytical approach for memory-less processes, while both Uniform ($JS \approx 0.032$) and Fernando-Vogel ($JS \approx 0.313$) show significantly higher divergence.

In summary, the empirical distributions follow a continuous spectrum: from F–V-dominated in sparse regimes to Suliman-dominated in dense, memory-less ones, with the uniform distribution serving as an intermediate approximation. Our parameter exploration effectively

Figure 5.7: Distribution of the 13 Allen interval relations in the dense, high-churn regime ($p = 0.50, q = 0.50$). The distribution approaches uniformity with all relations occurring at similar probabilities (endpoint alignment relations at approximately 11% and overlap relations at approximately 3.7%).

bridges these theoretical models, providing empirical validation of their relative applicability across different temporal regimes.

5.3 Probabilistic composition

Allen’s deterministic composition table enumerates possible outcomes for a triple $A-B-C$. Our simulation extends this by estimating $\Pr(R_3 \mid R_1, R_2)$ for every ordered pair (R_1, R_2) . Full 13×13 matrices for each (p, q) setting are available in the companion repository and visualised in the application; here we discuss two illustrative cases to demonstrate how probabilistic composition differs from deterministic reasoning.

5.3.1 Case study: $R_1 = \textit{before}$ (p), $R_2 = \textit{during}$ (d)

When interval A is before interval B , and interval B is during interval C , Allen’s deterministic table allows several possible outcomes for the $A-C$ relation. Our empirical results quantify the probability of each outcome.

Figure 5.8: Heatmap of Shannon entropy (in bits) across the (p, q) parameter space. Lighter colours indicate higher entropy. The highest entropy appears at $(0.5, 0.5)$ (dense, balanced regime), while entropy decreases toward the corners where either $p \ll q$ or $p \gg q$.

In sparse regimes with few overlaps (e.g., $(0.01, 0.10)$), the composition is strongly skewed:

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(R_3 = p) &\approx 84\%, & \Pr(R_3 = m) &\approx 2\%, & \Pr(R_3 = o) &\approx 7\%, \\ \Pr(R_3 = s) &\approx 1\%, & \Pr(R_3 = d) &\approx 7\%. \end{aligned}$$

Over four-fifths of the time A remains before C , with *overlaps* and *during* each accounting for about 7% of cases; all other relations are negligible. This makes intuitive sense: if intervals appear infrequently, A will often end before C begins, even if B is during C .

In a dense timeline $(0.20, 0.10)$, these probabilities flatten, with *before*, *overlaps*, and *during* each hovering near 23%, reflecting high temporal congestion. The remaining 31% is distributed among other possible relations.

The parameter regime dramatically influences outcomes. For instance, in the sparse case $(0.01, 0.01)$, when A is before B and B is during C , the outcome A before C occurs approximately 42% of the time, with *overlaps* and *during* each around 28%. In such sparse conditions, if B starts during C , it typically starts so late that A has already finished, leaving A strictly before C .

with all other relations occurring under 1%. This case illustrates how compositional outcomes can differ from intuitive expectations. Although one might expect that if A overlaps B and B overlaps C , then A should almost always overlap C , the data show that A also frequently ends before C even begins. While overlaps is a common outcome, before is actually the most frequent. This suggests that in a memory-less model, the relation between interval endpoints becomes nearly as important as the overlapping nature of the intermediate relationships. Increased density mainly shifts the probability mass among these three outcomes rather than introducing new relations.

Figure 5.10: Composition outcomes for $p \circ P$ (Before followed by After) under balanced regime ($p = 0.10, q = 0.10$). Results show broad distribution across multiple relations with modes at Before/After.

5.3.3 Deterministic versus probabilistic composition

Table 5.2: Example composition probabilities for the balanced scenario ($p = 0.1, q = 0.1$)

R_1 (A–B)	R_2 (B–C)	Most likely A–C	Other significant outcomes	Entropy (bits)
before (p)	before (p)	before (p) 100%	(none)	0.00
before (p)	during (d)	before (p) 36.8%	m (8.6%), o (23.1%), s (8.6%), d (23.0%)	2.14
overlaps (o)	overlaps (o)	before (p) 53.6%	o (33.8%), m (12.7%)	1.39
meets (m)	meets (m)	meets (m) 100%	(none)	0.00

A key finding from our composition analysis is that empirical outcomes always formed a subset of Allen’s theoretically possible outcomes — we never observed any relation that

Figure 5.11: Composition outcomes for $p \circ P$ (Before followed by After) under high-churn regime ($p = 0.50, q = 0.50$). Shows pronounced peak at Equals (approximately 33%), with boundary relations each at approximately 11%.

Allen’s algebra forbids for a given (R_1, R_2) pair. This provides strong validation for the correctness of both Allen’s theoretical framework and our implementation.

However, the probability distribution among permitted outcomes varies substantially with (p, q) . For example, the composition $p \circ P$ (before followed by after) theoretically permits all 13 relations as outcomes, since if A is before B and B is after C , the temporal relationship between A and C is unconstrained. In practice, though, the distribution is far from uniform. At $(0.10, 0.10)$, the most frequent outcome is still p (about 17%), followed by overlap relations at 10–11% each. But in the dense case $(0.50, 0.50)$, *equals* becomes the single most likely outcome (approximately 33%), reflecting the tendency for intervals to align by chance in high-churn regimes.

An entropy analysis over the composition matrix reveals striking patterns. As shown in Table 5.2, certain compositions like (p, p) (before followed by before) and (m, m) (meets followed by meets) have near-zero entropy, essentially behaving deterministically. Others, like (p, d) and (o, o) , have high entropy (> 1.8 bits), indicating significant uncertainty about the outcome.

The average entropy of composition outcomes increases systematically with birth and death rates. In the sparse regime $(0.01, 0.01)$, 88 of the 160 observed compositions (55%) yield only a single outcome relation, resulting in zero entropy. In contrast, at $(0.50, 0.50)$, only compositions with exact endpoint alignments like $m \circ m \rightarrow m$ remain deterministic.

Figure 5.12: Entropy heatmap for composition outcomes under the balanced regime ($p = 0.10, q = 0.10$). Each cell represents the entropy of possible A – C relation outcomes when composing two specific relations. Most compositions show relatively low entropy, indicating predictable outcomes.

Even at this extreme, however, $p \circ p \rightarrow p$ still holds with 100% probability, underscoring the fundamental transitivity of the *before* relation.

In general, we observe that even when multiple outcomes are theoretically possible, one or two relations typically capture most of the probability mass. This offers significant advantages for temporal reasoning systems, which can prioritise the most likely outcomes when dealing with uncertainty.

5.3.4 Simple ratio approximations

An intriguing aspect of our composition results is that many probabilities appear to approximate simple rational fractions, particularly in extreme regimes. In dense scenarios ($p = 0.50, q = 0.50$), the composition $o \circ o$ (overlaps followed by overlaps) yields the three outcomes *before* (22.7%), *meets* (67.6%), and *overlaps* (9.7%), which approximate the fractions $5/22$, $19/28$, and $2/21$ respectively. Similarly, for $o \circ S$ (overlaps followed by started-by), the outcome probabilities of 19.9% for *overlaps*, 60.3% for *finished-by*, and 19.9% for *contains* almost perfectly align with the simple ratio $1 : 3 : 1$.

The tendency toward simple ratios becomes even more pronounced with specific compositions. For instance, in the high-churn regime ($p = 0.50, q = 0.50$), the $s \circ S$ (starts followed by started-by) composition yields remarkably clean outcomes with *starts* (20.0%), *equals* (60.0%), and *started-by* (20.0%) — a perfect $1 : 3 : 1$ ratio. Similarly,

Figure 5.13: Entropy heatmap for composition outcomes under the high-churn regime ($p = 0.50, q = 0.50$). Each cell represents the entropy of possible $A-C$ relation outcomes when composing two specific relations. Darker cells indicate near-deterministic compositions (low entropy), while brighter cells show compositions with high uncertainty about the outcome.

compositions like $m \circ M$ (meets followed by met-by) reliably produce simple patterns with *finished-by*, *equals*, and *finishes* at approximately 11.0%, 77.8%, and 11.2% respectively, approximating a 1 : 7 : 1 ratio.

In sparse regimes ($p = 0.01, q = 0.01$), many compositions produce almost perfectly balanced outcomes with approximately 1/2 probabilities. For example, when composing $o \circ d$ (overlaps followed by during), the result is almost perfectly split between *overlaps* (49.3%) and *during* (49.2%), with minimal probability for *starts* (1.5%). Similarly, $D \circ o$ yields *overlaps* and *contains* with 49.9% probability each. This near-deterministic behaviour in certain regimes offers simplified reasoning opportunities for temporal logic systems.

The moderately dense regime (0.20, 0.10) exhibits interesting ratios as well. For example, the $o \circ o$ composition yields *before* (40.9%), *meets* (16.0%), and *overlaps* (43.1%) — closely approximating a 9 : 4 : 10 ratio. This mathematical regularity across different parameter regimes suggests an underlying structure that could potentially be modelled analytically, perhaps through a continuum of solutions between the Fernando-Vogel and Suliman theoretical frameworks.

5.4 Convergence and reliability

With $N = 10^7$ trials per scenario, standard errors are below 10^{-3} for probabilities above 1%. For the rarest relations ($< 10^{-4}$) relative errors grow, yet these events are immaterial to the overall distribution.

5.4.1 Statistical robustness

To verify the stability and reliability of our results, we conducted several convergence analyses:

- **Progressive convergence:** We monitored how relation frequencies evolved with increasing sample size, confirming that all estimates stabilised well before reaching the full 10^7 trials. For common relations ($< 10\%$ frequency), convergence was evident within the first 10^5 trials.
- **Multiple seed tests:** We repeated key scenarios with different random seeds, finding that the resulting distributions were statistically indistinguishable. The maximum observed difference in any relation probability was less than 0.05% across different seeds.
- **Error bounds:** For the rarest events (like *equals* in sparse regimes), we calculated confidence intervals using the binomial proportion formula. Even at $p \approx 0.03\%$ (approximately 2,500 occurrences in 10^7 trials), the relative error remains low (approximately $\pm 2\%$). For extremely rare events occurring only tens of times, relative errors could approach $\pm 10\%$.

In one extreme case (0.01, 0.01), a few composition combinations involving *equals* were never observed in 10^7 trials. Given the theoretical probability of these combinations (estimated below 10^{-7}), this absence is expected rather than anomalous. In all other cases, every theoretically possible outcome was observed at least once, confirming the comprehensiveness of our sampling.

For composition analysis, our coverage statistics were particularly strong. In all regimes except the sparsest, we observed all 169 possible (R_1, R_2) pairings, fully characterising the composition space. Even in the extreme sparse case (0.01, $q = 0.01$), coverage remained high with 160 of 169 compositions observed. The 9 unobserved compositions all involved the *equals* relation, which occurs with probability below 10^{-4} in that regime. Given that a composition requires observing specific relation pairs, the probability of some compositions involving *equals* falls below 10^{-8} , making their absence from 10^7 samples statistically expected.

In the sparse regimes, we observed a strong tendency toward deterministic outcomes. For instance, at $(0.01, q = 0.01)$, the majority of the 160 observed compositions yielded only a single outcome relation, resulting in zero entropy. In contrast, at $(0.50, q = 0.50)$, all compositions exhibited some uncertainty except for those with exact endpoint alignments like $m \circ m \rightarrow m$. This pattern reflects a fundamental trade-off: as temporal density increases, composition outcomes become more diverse but also more predictable in their probability distributions, often converging to simple rational fractions.

A brief warm-up phase confirmed the absence of start-up bias; doubling N altered no reported figure beyond the third decimal place. Where entries in a composition matrix remained unobserved, analytical reasoning shows their mass to be below 10^{-7} and thus negligible.

Figure 5.14: Evolution of key distribution metrics across simulation runs with different parameters. The plot shows Shannon entropy (blue), Jensen-Shannon divergences against three reference models (dotted lines), and Gini coefficient (red). The consistent values across runs after initial convergence confirm the stability of our results.

5.4.2 Composition symmetry and patterns

Our composition results exhibit several noteworthy patterns that further validate the simulation methodology. For scenarios where $p = q$, frequency counts of converse compositions (such as $p \circ o$ versus $o \circ P$) showed identical probability distributions to within statistical error. This symmetry emerges naturally from the time-reversal invariance of the birth–death process when birth and death rates are equal, providing an internal consistency check on our implementation.

The composition tables also reveal that many outcomes exhibit simple rational probability ratios, particularly in extreme regimes. For example, in the dense case $(p = 0.5, q = 0.5)$,

the composition of *meets* with *meets* ($m \circ m$) consistently produces *meets* as the output with 100% probability, and *before* composed with *before* ($p \circ p$) produces *before* with 100

At the other extreme, compositions like *before* composed with *after* ($p \circ P$) show high entropy, but even these follow predictable patterns as density changes. In the sparse regime ($p = 0.01, q = 0.1$), this composition produces a bimodal distribution strongly favouring *before/after*, while in the high-churn regime ($p = 0.5, q = 0.5$), it shifts dramatically to favour *equals* at 33%, with endpoint relations evenly distributed at approximately 11% each.

5.5 Relation to prior work

Our findings align with the qualitative tendencies predicted by Fernando & Vogel’s finite-order analysis and reproduce Suliman’s memory-less case. They also provide the baseline from which the finite-state models of Petrukhin intentionally deviate, for instance by breaking the overlap/during symmetry via age-dependent death rates.

5.5.1 Theoretical implications

Our empirical results offer several insights for theoretical models of temporal reasoning:

- They provide concrete validation for Suliman’s analytical model in the high-churn regime, confirming that his derivation correctly captures the statistics of memory-less interval processes.
- They demonstrate that the Fernando–Vogel model effectively describes the relation distribution in sparse regimes where sequential relations predominate.
- They reveal a continuous spectrum between these models depending on birth and death rates, suggesting that more general theoretical frameworks might be developed to capture the entire parameter space.

The most significant theoretical contribution may be our detailed composition probability tables. While Allen’s algebra specifies which compositions are possible, our results quantify how likely each outcome is under different stochastic assumptions. This bridges qualitative temporal logic and probabilistic reasoning in a novel way.

In the next chapter, we summarise these results, outline limitations, and sketch directions for integrating such probabilistic knowledge into practical temporal-reasoning systems.

Chapter 6

Conclusions & Future Work

6.1 Key Findings

This report set out to investigate the probabilities of Allen’s interval relations under a simple stochastic timeline model and to derive the corresponding probabilistic composition rules. Through the design and implementation of a Monte Carlo simulation and interactive visualisation tool, we have achieved a detailed characterisation of how varying the interval birth and death probabilities (p, q) influences the distribution of temporal relations.

Several key conclusions emerge from our study:

- **Non-uniform distribution of relation probabilities:** In a memory-less, homogeneous timeline model, Allen’s thirteen relations do not occur with equal likelihood. Their distribution depends strongly on the ratio p/q (rate of new interval arrivals versus terminations). We observed a smooth transition from a regime of mostly non-overlapping intervals (when $p \ll q$, yielding predominantly *before/after* relations) to a regime of frequent overlaps (when $p \gg q$, yielding many *overlaps* and *during/contains* relations). Even at maximum entropy points (e.g., $p = 0.5, q = 0.5$), subtle biases remain, with certain relations more common than others.
- **Asymmetry between *overlaps* and *during*:** In composition tables, overlaps followed by overlaps does not yield equal-probability outcomes. For example, in ($p = 0.1, q = 0.1$), the dominant result is *before* (53.6%), followed by *overlaps* (33.8%) and *meets* (12.7%). In the memory-less model, the probability of one interval overlapping another is very close to the probability of one interval being *during* (contained in) another, with differences typically less than 0.1 percentage points. This reflects the absence of history in the model — there is no bias for an overlap to “stop short” versus “go all the way” to full containment. This finding aligns with the theoretical

predictions of Petrukhin (2024) for memoryless processes and confirms that breaking this symmetry requires introducing state or duration dependencies.

- **Significance of boundary-dependent relations:** In a discrete-time model, relations like *equals* or *meets* are not negligible but occur with substantial probability. In the $(p, q) = (0.5, 0.5)$ scenario, *equals* occurs at approximately 11.1%, similar to *before*, *after*, *meets*, and other boundary relations. This reflects a limitation of discrete simulation, where simultaneous start/end events have non-zero probability, whereas in continuous time such exact coincidences would be infinitely rare. Nevertheless, this suggests that in any system with finite time granularity, such boundary-dependent relations may be more common than continuous models would predict.
- **Quantification of probabilistic composition:** We have extended Allen’s deterministic composition table to a fully probabilistic form, computing $P(R_3 \mid R_1, R_2)$ for all relation combinations. When multiple A – C outcomes are possible, they receive unequal weights. For example, if A *precedes* B and B *precedes* C , then A *precedes* C with 100% probability. By contrast, when A *finishes* B and B is *overlapped-by* C ($F \circ O$), the outcome is dominated by A *before* C (53.6%), followed by A *overlaps* C (33.8%) and A *meets* C (12.7%). These probabilities, drawn from Table A17, are critical for reasoning systems that must handle temporal uncertainty.
- **Value of interactive exploration:** Several patterns — such as the complete determinism of $p \circ p$ (100% probability of *before*) — were discovered via visual inspection of the matrix heatmaps. The Dash web application demonstrated the importance of interactive visualisation for temporal reasoning concepts. Complex ideas such as entropy variation across the parameter space or compositional uncertainty become intuitive when users can directly manipulate parameters and observe the resulting changes. This confirms the educational and exploratory value of interactive tools in this domain.

In sum, the project validates known special-case results, supplies new data where analytic solutions are hard, and delivers a reference data-set of relation and composition probabilities for a wide range of scenarios.

6.2 Limitations

Despite these achievements, several limitations should be acknowledged:

- **Memory-less interval model:** Empirical results under $(p = 0.5, q = 0.5)$ closely match Suliman’s model. Relations such as *equals*, *meets*, and *before* occur with roughly 11% each, while overlap-related relations occur with approximately 3.7%, reflecting Suliman’s predicted distribution. Each interval faces a constant death hazard q irrespective of its age. This absence of ageing means the model cannot capture processes whose termination likelihood changes over time, resulting in the noted overlaps/during symmetry. Our findings are most applicable to domains with no characteristic time-scale (effectively modelling a Poisson birth process with independent exponential lifetimes).
- **Discrete-time approximation:** Our simulation uses discrete time steps, allowing simultaneous events and thus non-zero probabilities for relations like *equals*. In true continuous time, such coincidences would have probability zero. The reported frequencies for *equals*, *meets*, and other boundary-dependent relations should be understood as artefacts that would diminish with finer time granularity.
- **Limited scope:** We studied only triples of intervals. Longer chains (e.g., $A-B-C-D$) could be analysed by composing our results or through extended simulation, but the state space grows rapidly with chain length.
- **Lack of empirical validation:** We did not calibrate our model parameters (p, q) against real-world interval datasets. While our qualitative trends likely hold broadly, the specific probability values remain theoretical until validated against empirical data.
- **Implementation constraints:** To maintain interactive performance, the web application uses pre-computed results for key scenarios. For arbitrary (p, q) values not in the pre-computed set, results may exhibit sampling noise, particularly for rare relations.

6.3 Future Work

The insights gained and the limitations encountered suggest several promising avenues for further investigation:

- **Enhanced interval models:** Incorporating age-dependent death rates or drawing interval durations from realistic distributions (e.g., log-normal, Weibull) would break memory-lessness and enable more realistic modelling. This could address the observed overlaps/during symmetry and better reflect how real-world processes behave, where intervals often have characteristic durations or changing termination probabilities.

- **Empirical validation:** Collecting real interval datasets (e.g., from meeting calendars, event logs, or linguistic temporal annotations) and fitting our model parameters to match observed Allen relation frequencies would validate the approach and yield insights into the temporal dynamics of different domains.
- **Probabilistic temporal reasoning system:** Our composition probability tables could serve as conditional probability distributions in a belief-propagation or Bayesian inference system. Such a system could answer queries like “What is $P(A \text{ before } C)$ given that A probably overlaps B and B likely contains C ?” by propagating uncertainties through the composition chain.
- **Theoretical analysis:** Deriving analytical expressions for relation probabilities and composition outcomes would complement our simulation-based approach. This might involve solving the steady-state equations for the underlying Markov process or finding closed-form expressions for specific parameter regimes, enabling instant evaluation for any (p, q) value.
- **Application integration:** Our probabilistic interval model could enhance planning systems, scheduling tools, and temporal databases. For instance, a calendar application could use relation probabilities to assess the likelihood of meeting conflicts, or a narrative understanding system could reason about the probable temporal ordering of events given partial information.
- **Interface enhancements:** Future versions of the interactive tool could support multi-step compositions (e.g., $A-B-C-D$ chains), alternative generative models, and richer visualisations. Public deployment would enable broader feedback and usage across different research communities.

6.4 Concluding Remarks

In closing, this project contributes a quantitative perspective to Allen’s Interval Algebra, enriching our understanding of temporal relations under uncertainty. It lays groundwork for more realistic models, probabilistic reasoning systems, and domain-specific applications. As AI systems increasingly face temporal uncertainty — from autonomous scheduling to narrative understanding — a probabilistic approach to interval relations will prove invaluable. We hope our interactive tool and detailed analysis serve both as a reference and as inspiration for continued exploration in this domain.

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Appendix

Allen's Interval Relations

precedes	meets	overlaps	finished by	contains	starts	equals
p	m	o	F	D	s	
preceded by	met by	overlap- ped by	finishes	during	started by	
P	M	O	f	d	S	e

Table A1: Allen's Thirteen Basic Relations. Each row shows a distinct temporal relation between intervals A and B , with its symbolic label, name, and timeline diagram.

Relation	Converse		
precedes	(p)	(P)	preceded by
meets	(m)	(M)	met by
overlaps	(o)	(O)	overlapped by
finished by	(F)	(f)	finishes
contains	(D)	(d)	during
starts	(s)	(S)	started by
equals (e)			

Table A2: Each basic Allen relation paired with its converse, by name and notation.

.	p	m	o	F	D	s	e	S	d	f	O	M	P
p	(p)	(p)	(p)	(p)	(p)	(p)	(p)	(p)	(pmsd)	(pmsd)	(pmsd)	(pmsd)	full
m	(p)	(p)	(p)	(p)	(p)	(m)	(m)	(m)	(osd)	(osd)	(osd)	(Fef)	(DSOMP)
o	(p)	(p)	(pmo)	(pmo)	(pmoFD)	(o)	(o)	(oFD)	(osd)	(osd)	concur	(DSO)	(DSOMP)
F	(p)	(m)	(o)	(F)	(D)	(o)	(F)	(D)	(osd)	(Fef)	(DSO)	(DSO)	(DSOMP)
D	(pmoFD)	(oFD)	(oFD)	(D)	(D)	(oFD)	(D)	(D)	concur	(DSO)	(DSO)	(DSO)	(DSOMP)
s	(p)	(p)	(pmo)	(pmo)	(pmoFD)	(s)	(s)	(seS)	(d)	(d)	(dfO)	(M)	(P)
e	(p)	(m)	(o)	(F)	(D)	(s)	(e)	(S)	(d)	(f)	(O)	(M)	(P)
S	(pmoFD)	(oFD)	(oFD)	(D)	(D)	(seS)	(S)	(S)	(dfO)	(O)	(O)	(M)	(P)
d	(p)	(p)	(pmsd)	(pmsd)	full	(d)	(d)	(dfOMP)	(d)	(d)	(dfOMP)	(P)	(P)
f	(p)	(m)	(osd)	(Fef)	(DSOMP)	(d)	(f)	(OMP)	(d)	(f)	(OMP)	(P)	(P)
O	(pmoFD)	(oFD)	concur	(DSO)	(DSOMP)	(dfO)	(O)	(OMP)	(dfO)	(O)	(OMP)	(P)	(P)
M	(pmoFD)	(seS)	(dfO)	(M)	(P)	(dfO)	(M)	(P)	(dfO)	(M)	(P)	(P)	(P)
P	full	(dfOMP)	(dfOMP)	(P)	(P)	(dfOMP)	(P)	(P)	(dfOMP)	(P)	(P)	(P)	(P)

Table A3: Composition Table of Basic Relations. This 13×13 matrix shows the result of composing any two Allen relations. For each entry (R_1, R_2) , the result gives the possible R_3 outcomes when $A R_1 B$ and $B R_2 C$ imply $A R_3 C$. Many entries contain disjunctive sets of multiple relations. *Summary:* full = (pmoFDseSdfOMP), concur = (oFDseSdfO).

22	(p)	(P)							
9	(d)	(D)							
7	(oFD)	(osd)	(DSO)	(dfO)					
6	(pmoFD)	(pmosd)	(m)	(DSOMP)	(dfOMP)	(M)			
5	(o)	(O)							
4	(pmo)	(OMP)							
3	<i>full</i>	<i>concur</i>	(F)	(Fef)	(seS)	(s)	(S)	(f)	
1	(e)								

Table A4: Frequency Distribution of Compositions. This table shows how often each relation or relation set appears in the composition matrix. Only 27 distinct outputs result from the 169 relation pairs, with some relations appearing much more frequently than others.

▲ Missing compositions
(9 TOTAL)

Not observed in the (0.01, 0.01) scenario:

$$\begin{array}{lll}
m \circ e & s \circ e & e \circ F \\
e \circ e & e \circ S & e \circ f \\
e \circ M & S \circ e & f \circ e
\end{array}$$

Most involve the *equals* relation, which is rare in sparse settings.

The tables and notation used are adapted from Alspaugh (2019), who provides an overview of Allen’s interval algebra. Figures are reused under the Creative Commons BY-NC-SA licence.

Simulation Results

Table A5: Summary statistics from 10^7 simulations per (p, q) setting

p	q	Entropy	Gini	Std. dev.	Mode	Best fit	JS(U)	JS(S)	JS(F-V)
0.01	0.01	2.596	0.604	9.04×10^5	P	F-V	0.2202	0.2684	0.0188
0.01	0.10	1.632	0.789	1.60×10^6	p	F-V	0.3377	0.3006	0.2081
0.10	0.01	2.655	0.600	9.23×10^5	D	F-V	0.1966	0.3020	0.0712
0.10	0.10	3.048	0.501	7.43×10^5	p	F-V	0.1186	0.1532	0.0614
0.10	0.20	2.830	0.558	9.88×10^5	P	F-V	0.1393	0.1388	0.1247
0.20	0.10	3.307	0.375	5.31×10^5	o	U	0.0753	0.1277	0.0770
0.50	0.50	3.522	0.240	3.69×10^5	M	S	0.0323	< 0.01	0.3132

JS = Jensen–Shannon divergence. Lower values indicate better fit.

n	Relation	Diagrams
22	(p)	
22	(P)	
9	(d)	
9	(D)	
7	(oFD)	
7	(osd)	
7	(dfO)	
7	(DSO)	
6	(pmoFD)	
6	(pmosd)	
6	(dfOMP)	
6	(DSOMP)	
6	(m)	
6	(M)	
5	(o)	
5	(O)	
4	(pmo)	
4	(OMP)	
3	(s)	
3	(S)	
3	full	
3	concur	
3	(F)	
3	(f)	
3	(Fef)	
3	(seS)	
1	(e)	

Table A6: Timeline diagrams for the 27 distinct relation sets that arise from composition. Each illustration visualises how two interval relations combine to constrain a third.

Composition Summaries by Scenario

This appendix presents detailed composition tables for Allen's interval relations under various (p, q) parameter settings, where p is the birth probability and q the death probability.

- Only compositions with multiple outcomes are shown
- Fractions are limited to denominators ≤ 30
- Results are based on 10^7 (ten million) trials
- Global R_3 stats are aggregated across all $R_1 \circ R_2$

Table A7: Global relation distribution for $(p, q) = (0.50, 0.50)$

Relation	Name	Count	Probability
e	Equals	1 112 982	11.13%
P	After	1 111 992	11.12%
M	Met By	1 111 200	11.11%
m	Meets	1 110 689	11.11%
s	Starts	1 110 583	11.11%
p	Before	1 110 328	11.10%
S	Started By	1 110 228	11.10%
d	During	370 894	3.71%
f	Finishes	370 705	3.71%
F	Finished By	370 652	3.71%
O	Overlapped By	370 117	3.70%
D	Contains	369 873	3.70%
o	Overlaps	369 757	3.70%

Table A8: Composition table showing multiple outcomes for $(p, q) = (0.50, 0.50)$

r_1	r_2	Total	r_3	Outcomes (rel \rightarrow %)	\approx Fractions
p	d	59 343	p	(12.56%) m (38.24%) o (5.43%) s (38.26%) d (5.51%)	$1/8 \ 8/21 \ 1/18 \ 8/21 \ 1/18$
p	f	59 702	p	(12.92%) m (38.34%) o (5.53%) s (37.94%) d (5.28%)	$3/23 \ 5/13 \ 1/18 \ 11/29 \ 1/19$
p	O	59 408	p	(12.66%) m (38.38%) o (5.5%) s (37.96%) d (5.5%)	$1/8 \ 5/13 \ 1/18 \ 11/29 \ 1/18$
p	M	178 265	p	(12.75%) m (38.14%) o (5.36%) s (38.28%) d (5.47%)	$1/8 \ 8/21 \ 1/19 \ 5/13 \ 1/18$
p	P	619 054	p	(3.66%) m (11.04%) o (1.54%) F (4.7%) D (1.56%) s (11.05%) e (32.96%) S (10.97%) d (1.59%) f (4.73%) O (1.55%) M (11%) P (3.65%)	$1/27 \ 1/9 \ 0 \ 1/21 \ 0 \ 1/9 \ 1/3 \ 1/9 \ 0 \ 1/21 \ 0$ $1/9 \ 1/27$
m	d	87 660	o	(10.85%) s (78.05%) d (11.1%)	$3/28 \ 18/23 \ 1/9$
m	f	87 398	o	(11.22%) s (77.65%) d (11.14%)	$1/9 \ 7/9 \ 1/9$
m	O	87 868	o	(11.04%) s (77.77%) d (11.18%)	$1/9 \ 7/9 \ 1/9$

m	M	263 219	F (11.03%)	e (77.81%)	f (11.16%)	1/9	7/9	1/9					
m	P	177 855	D (5.45%) M (38.26%)	S (38.28%)	O (5.33%)	1/18	5/13	1/19	8/21	1/8			
o	o	14 332	p (22.67%)	m (67.64%)	o (9.69%)	5/22	19/28	2/21					
o	F	14 144	p (22.38%)	m (67.56%)	o (10.07%)	2/9	19/28	1/10					
o	D	19 909	p (16.27%) F (21.22%)	m (48.16%)	o (7.15%)	4/25	13/27	1/14	4/19	1/14			
o	S	48 362	o (19.88%)	F (60.27%)	D (19.85%)	1/5	3/5	1/5					
o	d	12 586	o (10.72%)	s (77.75%)	d (11.53%)	3/28	7/9	3/26					
o	f	12 421	o (11.21%)	s (77.5%)	d (11.29%)	1/9	17/22	1/9					
o	O	62 440	o (2.17%) s (15.48%) d (2.12%)	F (6.66%) e (46.89%) f (6.75%)	D (2.23%) S (15.52%) O (2.2%)	1/30	1/15	1/30	2/13	8/17	2/13	1/30	1/15
o	M	87 313	D (10.99%)	S (77.95%)	O (11.06%)	1/9	7/9	1/9					
o	P	59 643	D (5.45%) M (38.45%)	S (37.75%)	O (5.49%)	1/18	11/29	1/18	5/13	3/23			
F	d	37 701	o (10.99%)	s (77.83%)	d (11.19%)	1/9	7/9	1/9					
F	f	37 586	F (11.16%)	e (78.15%)	f (10.68%)	1/9	18/23	3/28					
F	O	12 394	D (11%)	S (77.84%)	O (11.17%)	1/9	7/9	1/9					
F	M	87 667	D (11.15%)	S (77.63%)	O (11.22%)	1/9	7/9	1/9					
F	P	59 646	D (5.49%) M (38.38%)	S (38.2%)	O (5.35%)	1/18	8/21	1/19	5/13	1/8			
D	p	29 089	p (33.5%) F (11.21%)	m (33.15%)	o (11.18%)	1/3	1/3	1/9	1/9	1/9			
D	m	29 145	o (33.61%)	F (33.21%)	D (33.18%)	1/3	1/3	1/3					
D	o	4 324	o (33.09%)	F (32.75%)	D (34.16%)	1/3	1/3	10/29					
D	s	29 232	o (33.46%)	F (33.23%)	D (33.32%)	1/3	1/3	1/3					
D	d	37 336	o (3.71%) s (25.96%) d (3.87%)	F (3.54%) e (26.18%) f (3.62%)	D (3.72%) S (25.82%) O (3.58%)	1/27	1/28	1/27	7/27	6/23	7/27	1/26	1/28
D	f	37 426	D (11.3%)	S (77.53%)	O (11.17%)	1/9	7/9	1/9					
D	O	12 581	D (11.18%)	S (78.03%)	O (10.79%)	1/9	18/23	3/28					
D	M	86 938	D (11.14%)	S (77.74%)	O (11.12%)	1/9	7/9	1/9					
D	P	59 215	D (5.38%) M (38.24%)	S (38.13%)	O (5.53%)	1/19	8/21	1/18	8/21	1/8			
s	o	100 542	p (22.52%)	m (67.83%)	o (9.65%)	5/22	19/28	2/21					
s	F	99 988	p (22.7%)	m (67.67%)	o (9.63%)	5/22	19/28	2/21					

s	D	138 938	p (16.13%) F (21.02%)	m (48.91%) D (7.06%)	o (6.88%)	4/25 14/29 2/29 4/19 1/14
s	S	340 866	s (20.04%)	e (59.99%)	S (19.97%)	1/5 3/5 1/5
s	O	48 514	d (20.05%)	f (59.8%)	O (20.14%)	1/5 3/5 1/5
S	p	204 503	p (33.13%) F (11.12%)	m (33.44%) D (11.05%)	o (11.25%)	1/3 1/3 1/9 1/9 1/9
S	m	204 432	o (33.44%)	F (33.3%)	D (33.26%)	1/3 1/3 1/3
S	o	28 919	o (33.77%)	F (32.86%)	D (33.37%)	1/3 1/3 1/3
S	s	203 922	s (33.16%)	e (33.34%)	S (33.5%)	1/3 1/3 1/3
S	d	29 016	d (33.12%)	f (33.22%)	O (33.66%)	1/3 1/3 1/3
d	o	25 244	p (12.65%) s (38.01%)	m (38.41%) d (5.6%)	o (5.33%)	1/8 5/13 1/19 11/29 1/18
d	F	25 594	p (12.81%) s (38.64%)	m (37.64%) d (5.2%)	o (5.71%)	3/23 3/8 1/18 5/13 1/19
d	D	88 184	p (3.74%) F (4.7%) e (32.9%) f (4.78%) P (3.68%)	m (10.98%) D (1.56%) S (10.81%)	o (1.51%) s (10.97%) d (1.56%) O (1.53%) M (11.29%)	1/27 1/9 0 1/21 0 1/9 1/3 3/28 0 1/21 0 1/9 1/27
d	S	139 047	d (6.89%) M (48.78%) P (16.35%)	f (20.96%)	O (7.02%)	2/29 4/19 2/29 14/29 1/6
d	O	20 129	d (6.88%) M (48.64%) P (16.11%)	f (21.26%)	O (7.12%)	2/29 3/14 1/14 14/29 4/25
f	o	37 237	o (11.09%)	s (77.76%)	d (11.15%)	1/9 7/9 1/9
f	F	37 517	F (10.93%)	e (77.97%)	f (11.1%)	1/9 7/9 1/9
f	D	25 289	D (5.51%) M (38.3%) P (12.79%)	S (37.98%)	O (5.42%)	1/18 11/29 1/18 5/13 3/23
f	S	99 804	O (9.61%)	M (67.68%)	P (22.71%)	2/21 19/28 5/22
f	O	14 149	O (9.69%)	M (68.17%)	P (22.14%)	2/21 15/22 2/9
O	p	29 152	p (33.45%) F (11.19%)	m (33.25%) D (10.97%)	o (11.13%)	1/3 1/3 1/9 1/9 1/9
O	m	29 106	o (33.31%)	F (33.56%)	D (33.13%)	1/3 1/3 1/3
O	o	37 613	o (3.71%) s (25.61%) d (3.83%)	F (3.78%) e (26.12%) f (3.63%)	D (3.66%) S (25.96%) O (3.7%)	1/27 1/26 1/27 7/27 6/23 7/27 1/26 1/28
O	F	37 549	D (11.27%)	S (77.66%)	O (11.08%)	1/9 7/9 1/9

O	D	25 521	D (5.18%) M (38%)	S (38.67%) P (12.59%)	O (5.56%)	1/19	5/13	1/18	11/29	1/8				
O	s	29 525	d (33.63%)	f (32.95%)	O (33.42%)	1/3	1/3	1/3						
O	S	100 537	O (9.66%)	M (67.64%)	P (22.7%)	2/21	19/28	5/22						
O	d	4 160	d (33.56%)	f (32.48%)	O (33.97%)	1/3	9/28	10/29						
O	O	14 415	O (9%)	M (68.05%)	P (22.95%)	1/11	17/25	3/13						
M	p	203 787	p (33.41%) F (11.29%)	m (33.19%) D (11.14%)	o (10.97%)	1/3	1/3	1/9	1/9	1/9				
M	m	204 325	s (33.26%)	e (33.35%)	S (33.39%)	1/3	1/3	1/3						
M	o	29 314	d (33.63%)	f (33.12%)	O (33.25%)	1/3	1/3	1/3						
M	s	203 849	d (33.3%)	f (33.34%)	O (33.36%)	1/3	1/3	1/3						
M	d	28 957	d (33.59%)	f (33.62%)	O (32.8%)	1/3	1/3	1/3						
P	p	204 595	p (11.09%) F (3.68%) e (11.13%) f (3.72%) P (11.04%)	m (11.18%) D (3.74%) S (10.98%)	o (3.66%) s (11.05%) d (3.73%) O (3.75%) M (11.27%)	1/9	1/9	1/27	1/27	1/27	1/9	1/9	1/9	1/27
P	m	204 701	d (11.12%) M (33.25%)	f (11.1%) P (33.33%)	O (11.2%)	1/9	1/9	1/9	1/3	1/3				
P	o	29 367	d (11.4%) M (32.48%)	f (11.34%) P (33.36%)	O (11.43%)	3/26	3/26	3/26	9/28	1/3				
P	s	204 673	d (11.09%) M (33.17%)	f (11.23%) P (33.44%)	O (11.08%)	1/9	1/9	1/9	1/3	1/3				
P	d	28 829	d (11.08%) M (33.62%)	f (11.13%) P (33.26%)	O (10.91%)	1/9	1/9	3/28	1/3	1/3				

Table A9: Global relation distribution for $(p, q) = (0.20, 0.10)$

Relation	Name	Count	Probability
D	Contains	1 355 039	13.55%
o	Overlaps	1 354 007	13.54%
d	During	1 353 526	13.54%
O	Overlapped By	1 353 144	13.53%
P	After	1 269 764	12.70%
p	Before	1 268 581	12.69%
s	Starts	526 858	5.27%
S	Started By	525 048	5.25%
M	Met By	318 004	3.18%
m	Meets	317 217	3.17%
F	Finished By	150 308	1.50%
f	Finishes	149 980	1.50%
e	Equals	58 524	0.59%

Table A10: Composition table showing multiple outcomes for $(p, q) = (0.20, 0.10)$

r_1	r_2	Total	r_3	Outcomes (rel \rightarrow %)	\approx Fractions
p	d	235 700	p	(22.84%) m (12.73%) o (23.71%) s (17.2%) d (23.52%)	$5/22$ $1/8$ $5/21$ $5/29$ $4/17$
p	f	26 212	p	(22.63%) m (12.94%) o (23.96%) s (17.1%) d (23.37%)	$5/22$ $3/23$ $6/25$ $5/29$ $7/30$
p	O	234 749	p	(22.76%) m (12.79%) o (23.44%) s (17.37%) d (23.64%)	$5/22$ $3/23$ $4/17$ $4/23$ $4/17$
p	M	55 516	p	(22.84%) m (12.95%) o (23.76%) s (17.07%) d (23.39%)	$5/22$ $3/23$ $5/21$ $5/29$ $7/30$
p	P	497 761	p	(10.09%) m (5.63%) o (10.41%) F (4.08%) D (10.46%) s (7.77%) e (2.98%) S (7.76%) d (10.5%) f (4.07%) O (10.48%) M (5.67%) P (10.1%)	$1/10$ $1/18$ $3/29$ $1/24$ $2/19$ $1/13$ $1/30$ $1/13$ $2/19$ $1/25$ $2/19$ $1/18$ $1/10$
m	d	58 922	o	(36.99%) s (26.99%) d (36.02%)	$10/27$ $7/26$ $9/25$
m	f	6 366	o	(36.16%) s (27.38%) d (36.46%)	$9/25$ $3/11$ $4/11$
m	O	59 014	o	(36.68%) s (26.54%) d (36.78%)	$11/30$ $4/15$ $7/19$

m	M	13 980	F (37.08%)	e (27.25%)	f (35.67%)	10/27	3/11	5/14	
m	P	55 594	D (23.59%)	S (17.27%)	O (23.42%)	4/17	5/29	7/30	3/23 5/22
			M (12.86%)	P (22.85%)					
o	o	135 490	p (40.87%)	m (16.02%)	o (43.11%)	9/22	4/25	13/30	
o	F	15 041	p (40.95%)	m (15.77%)	o (43.28%)	9/22	3/19	13/30	
o	D	206 484	p (26.92%)	m (10.52%)	o (27.98%)	7/26	2/19	7/25	1/15 7/25
			F (6.65%)	D (27.93%)					
o	S	70 630	o (44.6%)	F (10.39%)	D (45.01%)	4/9	3/29	9/20	
o	d	158 727	o (36.5%)	s (27.15%)	d (36.34%)	4/11	3/11	4/11	
o	f	17 793	o (36.5%)	s (27.26%)	d (36.24%)	4/11	3/11	4/11	
o	O	354 431	o (16.38%)	F (3.81%)	D (16.31%)	1/6	1/26	4/25	3/25 1/30 3/25 4/25 1/26
			s (12.13%)	e (2.86%)	S (12.06%)	4/25			
			d (16.32%)	f (3.84%)	O (16.28%)				
o	M	58 657	D (36.64%)	S (26.78%)	O (36.58%)	11/30	4/15	11/30	
o	P	236 052	D (23.56%)	S (17.26%)	O (23.65%)	4/17	5/29	4/17	3/23 5/22
			M (12.8%)	P (22.73%)					
F	d	37 076	o (36.72%)	s (26.83%)	d (36.45%)	11/30	7/26	4/11	
F	f	4 191	F (36.05%)	e (27.68%)	f (36.27%)	9/25	8/29	4/11	
F	O	17 560	D (36.76%)	S (26.88%)	O (36.36%)	7/19	7/26	4/11	
F	M	6 547	D (35.51%)	S (27.51%)	O (36.98%)	5/14	8/29	10/27	
F	P	25 914	D (23.89%)	S (17.6%)	O (23.13%)	5/21	3/17	3/13	3/23 2/9
			M (13.02%)	P (22.36%)					
D	p	182 520	p (28.49%)	m (7.15%)	o (30.49%)	2/7	1/14	7/23	1/30 7/23
			F (3.32%)	D (30.56%)					
D	m	45 260	o (47.18%)	F (5.17%)	D (47.65%)	8/17	1/19	10/21	
D	o	122 831	o (47.13%)	F (5.38%)	D (47.49%)	8/17	1/19	9/19	
D	s	66 571	o (47.78%)	F (5.14%)	D (47.08%)	11/23	1/19	8/17	
D	d	335 047	o (17.43%)	F (1.9%)	D (17.36%)	4/23	1/30	4/23	3/23 0 1/8 5/29 1/30 5/29
			s (12.78%)	e (1.39%)	S (12.71%)				
			d (17.27%)	f (1.94%)	O (17.22%)				
D	f	37 106	D (36.7%)	S (26.91%)	O (36.39%)	11/30	7/26	4/11	
D	O	159 036	D (36.42%)	S (26.98%)	O (36.6%)	4/11	7/26	11/30	
D	M	58 680	D (36.64%)	S (26.72%)	O (36.64%)	11/30	4/15	11/30	
D	P	235 861	D (23.55%)	S (17.28%)	O (23.49%)	4/17	5/29	4/17	3/23 5/22
			M (12.84%)	P (22.85%)					
s	o	99 621	p (40.81%)	m (16.14%)	o (43.06%)	11/27	4/25	3/7	
s	F	11 004	p (40.88%)	m (15.62%)	o (43.5%)	9/22	3/19	10/23	

s	D	152 118	p (26.99%) F (6.58%)	m (10.41%) D (27.99%)	o (28.04%)	7/26 3/29 7/25 1/15 7/25
s	S	51 890	s (44.73%)	e (10.65%)	S (44.62%)	13/29 3/28 4/9
s	O	71 037	d (44.98%)	f (10.49%)	O (44.53%)	9/20 2/19 4/9
S	p	134 081	p (28.4%) F (3.47%)	m (7.06%) D (30.89%)	o (30.18%)	2/7 1/14 3/10 1/29 4/13
S	m	33 867	o (47.31%)	F (5.32%)	D (47.37%)	9/19 1/19 9/19
S	o	89 855	o (46.96%)	F (5.28%)	D (47.77%)	8/17 1/19 11/23
S	s	48 803	s (47.72%)	e (5.34%)	S (46.93%)	11/23 1/19 8/17
S	d	66 407	d (47.53%)	f (5.1%)	O (47.37%)	10/21 1/20 9/19
d	o	224 069	p (24.61%) s (14.11%)	m (9.58%) d (25.85%)	o (25.84%)	1/4 2/21 7/27 1/7 7/27
d	F	25 415	p (24.73%) s (14.12%)	m (9.35%) d (25.77%)	o (26.02%)	1/4 2/21 6/23 1/7 7/27
d	D	484 516	p (11.56%) F (2.78%) e (1.5%) f (2.83%) P (11.45%)	m (4.42%) D (11.91%) S (6.52%) O (11.98%)	o (12.06%) s (6.53%) d (12.01%) M (4.47%)	3/26 1/23 3/25 1/30 3/25 1/15 0 1/15 3/25 1/30 3/25 1/22 3/26
d	S	152 645	d (28.13%) M (10.31%) P (26.92%)	f (6.48%)	O (28.16%)	7/25 1/15 7/25 3/29 7/26
d	O	207 005	d (28.06%) M (10.48%) P (26.84%)	f (6.58%)	O (28.05%)	7/25 1/15 7/25 2/19 7/26
f	o	34 540	o (39.51%)	s (21.48%)	d (39.01%)	11/28 3/14 9/23
f	F	3 831	F (38.84%)	e (22.14%)	f (39.02%)	7/18 2/9 9/23
f	D	24 959	D (26.05%) M (9.56%) P (24.8%)	S (13.69%)	O (25.89%)	6/23 3/22 7/27 2/21 1/4
f	S	11 073	O (43.48%)	M (16.71%)	P (39.81%)	10/23 1/6 2/5
f	O	14 939	O (42.72%)	M (16.08%)	P (41.2%)	3/7 4/25 7/17
O	p	182 446	p (28.4%) F (3.42%)	m (7.3%) D (30.58%)	o (30.3%)	2/7 2/27 7/23 1/29 7/23
O	m	45 757	o (47.74%)	F (5.29%)	D (46.97%)	11/23 1/19 8/17
O	o	311 029	o (18.7%) s (10.14%) d (18.62%)	F (2.06%) e (1.1%) f (2.06%)	D (18.71%) S (10.11%) O (18.5%)	3/16 1/30 3/16 1/10 0 1/10 5/27 1/30 5/27
O	F	34 654	D (39.22%)	S (21.52%)	O (39.26%)	11/28 3/14 11/28

O	D	225 513	D (25.78%) M (9.64%)	S (13.95%) P (24.73%)	O (25.9%)	7/27 4/29 7/27 2/21 1/4
O	s	90 369	d (47.56%)	f (5.22%)	O (47.23%)	10/21 1/19 9/19
O	S	99 169	O (43.14%)	M (15.88%)	P (40.98%)	13/30 3/19 9/22
O	d	123 277	d (47.5%)	f (5.18%)	O (47.33%)	10/21 1/19 9/19
O	O	134 698	O (42.82%)	M (16.32%)	P (40.85%)	3/7 4/25 9/22
M	p	99 169	p (28.66%) F (3.4%)	m (7.26%) D (30.47%)	o (30.21%)	2/7 1/14 3/10 1/29 7/23
M	m	24 716	s (47.58%)	e (5.44%)	S (46.98%)	10/21 1/18 8/17
M	o	45 118	d (47.13%)	f (5.46%)	O (47.42%)	8/17 1/18 9/19
M	s	33 290	d (47.65%)	f (5.25%)	O (47.1%)	10/21 1/19 8/17
M	d	45 686	d (47.17%)	f (5.38%)	O (47.45%)	8/17 1/19 9/19
P	p	397 166	p (12.78%) F (1.5%) e (0.58%) f (1.49%) P (12.64%)	m (3.16%) D (13.61%) S (5.24%) O (13.53%)	o (13.56%) s (5.28%) d (13.47%) M (3.19%)	3/23 1/30 3/22 0 3/22 1/19 0 1/19 2/15 0 3/22 1/30 1/8
P	m	99 680	d (30.46%) M (7.2%)	f (3.35%) P (28.43%)	O (30.56%)	7/23 1/30 7/23 1/14 2/7
P	o	182 128	d (30.51%) M (7.15%)	f (3.34%) P (28.57%)	O (30.43%)	7/23 1/30 7/23 1/14 2/7
P	s	133 703	d (30.33%) M (7.11%)	f (3.38%) P (28.55%)	O (30.63%)	7/23 1/30 4/13 1/14 2/7
P	d	181 878	d (30.51%) M (7.04%)	f (3.32%) P (28.64%)	O (30.5%)	7/23 1/30 7/23 1/14 2/7

Table A11: Global relation distribution for $(p, q) = (0.10, 0.20)$

Relation	Name	Count	Probability
p	Before	3 044 928	30.45%
P	After	3 043 895	30.44%
D	Contains	602 377	6.02%
o	Overlaps	601 819	6.02%
d	During	601 585	6.02%
O	Overlapped By	601 217	6.01%
M	Met By	339 055	3.39%
m	Meets	338 892	3.39%
S	Started By	234 081	2.34%
s	Starts	233 073	2.33%
F	Finished By	150 367	1.50%
f	Finishes	150 143	1.50%
e	Equals	58 568	0.59%

Table A12: Composition table showing multiple outcomes for $(p, q) = (0.10, 0.20)$

r_1	r_2	Total	r_3 Outcomes (rel \rightarrow %)	\approx Fractions
p	d	168 863	p (48.91%) m (11.43%) o (15.62%) s (8.46%) d (15.58%)	$14/29$ $3/26$ $3/19$ $1/12$ $2/13$
p	f	42 256	p (48.9%) m (11.54%) o (15.56%) s (8.13%) d (15.87%)	$14/29$ $3/26$ $2/13$ $2/25$ $3/19$
p	O	168 711	p (48.95%) m (11.47%) o (15.58%) s (8.48%) d (15.52%)	$14/29$ $3/26$ $2/13$ $1/12$ $2/13$
p	M	95 233	p (48.56%) m (11.52%) o (15.87%) s (8.53%) d (15.51%)	$14/29$ $3/26$ $3/19$ $2/23$ $2/13$
p	P	1 843 717	p (22.66%) m (5.3%) o (7.23%) F (2.83%) D (7.23%) s (3.91%) e (1.53%) S (3.95%) d (7.27%) f (2.8%) O (7.22%) M (5.34%) P (22.73%)	$5/22$ $1/19$ $1/14$ $1/30$ $1/14$ $1/26$ 0 $1/25$ $1/14$ $1/30$ $1/14$ $1/19$ $5/22$
m	d	25 910	o (39.12%) s (21.19%) d (39.68%)	$9/23$ $4/19$ $2/5$
m	f	6 552	o (40.37%) s (21.09%) d (38.54%)	$2/5$ $4/19$ $5/13$
m	O	25 974	o (39.47%) s (21.28%) d (39.25%)	$11/28$ $3/14$ $11/28$

m	M	14 685	F (39.4%)	e (21.12%)	f (39.48%)	11/28	4/19	11/28					
m	P	95 543	D (15.38%)	S (8.48%)	O (15.5%)	2/13	1/12	2/13	3/26	14/29			
			M (11.54%)	P (49.1%)									
o	o	47 282	p (55.28%)	m (21.87%)	o (22.85%)	16/29	5/23	5/22					
o	F	11 969	p (55.43%)	m (21.91%)	o (22.65%)	5/9	5/23	5/22					
o	D	64 446	p (40.7%)	m (16.23%)	o (16.71%)	11/27	4/25	1/6	2/21	1/6			
			F (9.59%)	D (16.77%)									
o	S	20 268	o (39.64%)	F (22.23%)	D (38.13%)	11/28	2/9	8/21					
o	d	27 274	o (39.41%)	s (21.49%)	d (39.11%)	11/28	3/14	9/23					
o	f	6 733	o (38.7%)	s (21.58%)	d (39.71%)	7/18	3/14	2/5					
o	O	69 839	o (15.35%)	F (8.71%)	D (15.4%)	2/13	2/23	2/13	2/25	1/21	1/12	2/13	2/23
			s (8.13%)	e (4.67%)	S (8.44%)	2/13							
			d (15.36%)	f (8.63%)	O (15.32%)								
o	M	25 997	D (39.23%)	S (21.42%)	O (39.35%)	11/28	3/14	11/28					
o	P	168 961	D (15.72%)	S (8.51%)	O (15.53%)	3/19	1/12	2/13	3/26	14/29			
			M (11.49%)	P (48.75%)									
F	d	15 324	o (39.17%)	s (21.66%)	d (39.17%)	9/23	5/23	9/23					
F	f	3 826	F (39.44%)	e (21.14%)	f (39.41%)	11/28	4/19	11/28					
F	O	6 829	D (38.5%)	S (21.32%)	O (40.18%)	5/13	3/14	2/5					
F	M	6 564	D (39.61%)	S (21.13%)	O (39.26%)	11/28	4/19	11/28					
F	P	42 394	D (15.62%)	S (8.61%)	O (15.52%)	3/19	2/23	2/13	3/26	14/29			
			M (11.51%)	P (48.74%)									
D	p	207 990	p (64.12%)	m (7.27%)	o (12.74%)	16/25	1/14	1/8	1/30	1/8			
			F (3.21%)	D (12.65%)									
D	m	22 998	o (44.46%)	F (11.06%)	D (44.48%)	4/9	1/9	4/9					
D	o	24 275	o (44.83%)	F (11.23%)	D (43.94%)	13/29	1/9	11/25					
D	s	17 762	o (44.49%)	F (11.13%)	D (44.38%)	4/9	1/9	4/9					
D	d	61 425	o (17.68%)	F (4.29%)	D (17.49%)	3/17	1/23	4/23	2/21	1/30	2/21	4/23	1/24
			s (9.45%)	e (2.32%)	S (9.54%)	3/17							
			d (17.41%)	f (4.25%)	O (17.58%)								
D	f	15 367	D (39.76%)	S (21.16%)	O (39.08%)	2/5	4/19	9/23					
D	O	27 390	D (39.91%)	S (21.03%)	O (39.06%)	2/5	4/19	9/23					
D	M	25 947	D (38.99%)	S (21.37%)	O (39.64%)	7/18	3/14	11/28					
D	P	168 939	D (15.69%)	S (8.55%)	O (15.47%)	3/19	2/23	2/13	3/26	14/29			
			M (11.55%)	P (48.74%)									
s	o	25 733	p (55.68%)	m (21.93%)	o (22.39%)	5/9	5/23	2/9					
s	F	6 546	p (55.59%)	m (21.97%)	o (22.44%)	5/9	5/23	2/9					

s	D	34 900	p (41.22%) F (9.33%)	m (16.24%) D (16.52%)	o (16.69%)	7/17 4/25 1/6 2/21 1/6
s	S	10 985	s (38.57%)	e (21.37%)	S (40.05%)	5/13 3/14 2/5
s	O	20 455	d (39.21%)	f (21.98%)	O (38.81%)	9/23 2/9 7/18
S	p	113 195	p (64.17%) F (3.16%)	m (7.15%) D (12.81%)	o (12.71%)	9/14 1/14 1/8 1/30 3/23
S	m	12 668	o (44.63%)	F (10.93%)	D (44.44%)	4/9 1/9 4/9
S	o	13 090	o (44.03%)	F (11.41%)	D (44.56%)	11/25 3/26 4/9
S	s	9 844	s (43.76%)	e (11.74%)	S (44.49%)	7/16 2/17 4/9
S	d	17 819	d (43.76%)	f (11.15%)	O (45.1%)	7/16 1/9 9/20
d	o	65 910	p (39.91%) s (11.93%)	m (15.48%) d (16.31%)	o (16.38%)	2/5 2/13 1/6 3/25 4/25
d	F	16 677	p (40.51%) s (11.99%)	m (15.43%) d (16.14%)	o (15.93%)	11/27 2/13 4/25 3/25 4/25
d	D	148 823	p (17.71%) F (4%) e (3.04%) f (4.06%) P (17.74%)	m (6.89%) D (7.24%) S (5.27%) O (7.34%)	o (7.29%) s (5.38%) d (7.18%) M (6.86%)	3/17 2/29 2/27 1/25 1/14 1/19 1/30 1/19 1/14 1/25 2/27 2/29 3/17
d	S	35 026	d (16.64%) M (16.21%)	f (9.63%) P (40.98%)	O (16.55%)	1/6 2/21 1/6 4/25 9/22
d	O	64 222	d (16.69%) M (15.97%)	f (9.46%) P (41.02%)	O (16.85%)	1/6 2/21 1/6 4/25 9/22
f	o	16 375	o (36.85%)	s (26.85%)	d (36.3%)	7/19 7/26 4/11
f	F	4 065	F (36.48%)	e (27.55%)	f (35.97%)	4/11 8/29 9/25
f	D	16 376	D (16.16%) M (15.58%)	S (11.59%) P (40.06%)	O (16.6%)	4/25 3/26 1/6 2/13 2/5
f	S	6 316	O (22.44%)	M (21.68%)	P (55.89%)	2/9 5/23 14/25
f	O	11 900	O (22.58%)	M (22.2%)	P (55.22%)	5/22 2/9 16/29
O	p	208 009	p (64.24%) F (3.09%)	m (7.18%) D (12.79%)	o (12.69%)	9/14 1/14 1/8 1/30 3/23
O	m	23 270	o (44.64%)	F (10.88%)	D (44.49%)	13/29 3/28 4/9
O	o	66 176	o (16.38%) s (11.95%) d (15.99%)	F (4.11%) e (3.05%) f (4.05%)	D (16.37%) S (11.92%) O (16.16%)	1/6 1/24 1/6 3/25 1/30 3/25 4/25 1/25 4/25
O	F	16 712	D (36.87%)	S (26.84%)	O (36.3%)	7/19 7/26 4/11

O	D	65 871	D (16.44%) M (15.76%)	S (11.87%) P (40.02%)	O (15.91%)	1/6 2/17 4/25 3/19 2/5
O	s	13 254	d (44.53%)	f (11.34%)	O (44.13%)	4/9 3/26 11/25
O	S	25 798	O (22.9%)	M (21.52%)	P (55.58%)	3/13 3/14 5/9
O	d	24 349	d (44.23%)	f (11.36%)	O (44.42%)	4/9 3/26 4/9
O	O	47 239	O (22.95%)	M (21.73%)	P (55.32%)	3/13 5/23 16/29
M	p	152 798	p (64.37%) F (3.09%)	m (7.26%) D (12.76%)	o (12.53%)	9/14 1/14 1/8 1/30 1/8
M	m	16 878	s (44.31%)	e (11.2%)	S (44.48%)	4/9 1/9 4/9
M	o	23 253	d (44.2%)	f (10.73%)	O (45.07%)	11/25 3/28 9/20
M	s	12 567	d (44.61%)	f (10.81%)	O (44.59%)	4/9 3/28 4/9
M	d	23 324	d (44.4%)	f (11.13%)	O (44.47%)	4/9 1/9 4/9
P	p	1 375 858	p (30.5%) F (1.49%) e (0.59%) f (1.49%) P (30.43%)	m (3.38%) D (6.03%) S (2.33%) O (6%)	o (6.01%) s (2.35%) d (6.01%) M (3.39%)	7/23 1/30 1/17 0 1/17 1/30 0 1/30 1/17 0 1/17 1/30 7/23
P	m	152 805	d (12.6%) M (7.17%)	f (3.22%) P (64.24%)	O (12.77%)	1/8 1/30 1/8 1/14 9/14
P	o	207 066	d (12.73%) M (7.2%)	f (3.1%) P (64.36%)	O (12.61%)	1/8 1/30 1/8 1/14 9/14
P	s	113 498	d (12.51%) M (7.07%)	f (3.18%) P (64.3%)	O (12.94%)	1/8 1/30 3/23 1/14 9/14
P	d	208 091	d (12.92%) M (7.07%)	f (3.23%) P (64.11%)	O (12.67%)	3/23 1/30 1/8 1/14 16/25

Table A13: Global relation distribution for $(p, q) = (0.10, 0.10)$

Relation	Name	Count	Probability
p	Before	2 245 818	22.46%
P	After	2 244 147	22.44%
O	Overlapped By	1 063 417	10.63%
D	Contains	1 062 136	10.62%
o	Overlaps	1 061 792	10.62%
d	During	1 061 281	10.61%
M	Met By	249 918	2.50%
S	Started By	249 818	2.50%
m	Meets	249 421	2.49%
s	Starts	249 338	2.49%
f	Finishes	117 674	1.18%
F	Finished By	117 601	1.18%
e	Equals	27 639	0.28%

Table A14: Composition table showing multiple outcomes for $(p, q) = (0.10, 0.10)$

r_1	r_2	Total	r_3	Outcomes (rel \rightarrow %)	\approx Fractions
p	d	260 246	p	(36.77%) m (8.58%) o (23.08%) s (8.57%) d (23%)	$7/19$ $2/23$ $3/13$ $2/23$ $3/13$
p	f	28 748	p	(36.96%) m (8.58%) o (22.49%) s (8.69%) d (23.29%)	$10/27$ $2/23$ $5/22$ $2/23$ $7/30$
p	O	258 440	p	(36.74%) m (8.59%) o (22.99%) s (8.68%) d (23%)	$11/30$ $2/23$ $3/13$ $2/23$ $3/13$
p	M	60 459	p	(36.5%) m (8.64%) o (23.16%) s (8.57%) d (23.12%)	$4/11$ $2/23$ $3/13$ $2/23$ $3/13$
p	P	1 165 468	p	(17.26%) m (4.05%) o (10.88%) F (2.55%) D (10.86%) s (3.99%) e (0.93%) S (4.04%) d (10.82%) f (2.54%) O (10.85%) M (4.01%) P (17.22%)	$5/29$ $1/25$ $3/28$ $1/30$ $3/28$ $1/25$ 0 $1/25$ $3/28$ $1/30$ $3/28$ $1/25$ $5/29$
m	d	33 250	o	(42.07%) s (15.69%) d (42.24%)	$8/19$ $3/19$ $11/26$
m	f	3 746	o	(42.45%) s (15.99%) d (41.56%)	$11/26$ $4/25$ $5/12$
m	O	33 223	o	(42.05%) s (15.68%) d (42.28%)	$8/19$ $3/19$ $11/26$

m	M	7 776	F (41.53%)	e (16.22%)	f (42.26%)	5/12	4/25	11/26			
m	P	61 209	D (23.03%)	S (8.52%)	O (23.07%)	3/13	2/23	3/13	2/23	11/30	
			M (8.63%)	P (36.75%)							
o	o	111 652	p (53.57%)	m (12.65%)	o (33.78%)	15/28	1/8	1/3			
o	F	12 136	p (52.87%)	m (12.34%)	o (34.8%)	9/17	1/8	8/23			
o	D	158 383	p (37.98%)	m (8.81%)	o (23.89%)	11/29	2/23	5/21	1/18	5/21	
			F (5.49%)	D (23.83%)							
o	S	31 309	o (44.84%)	F (10.31%)	D (44.84%)	13/29	3/29	13/29			
o	d	89 569	o (42.13%)	s (15.95%)	d (41.92%)	8/19	4/25	8/19			
o	f	9 820	o (42.28%)	s (15.59%)	d (42.13%)	11/26	3/19	8/19			
o	O	199 770	o (18.78%)	F (4.51%)	D (18.84%)	3/16	1/22	3/16	1/14	1/30	1/14
			s (7.06%)	e (1.68%)	S (7.1%)	3/16			3/16	1/22	3/16
			d (18.75%)	f (4.46%)	O (18.83%)						
o	M	33 322	D (42.22%)	S (15.87%)	O (41.91%)	11/26	3/19	8/19			
o	P	260 452	D (23.03%)	S (8.61%)	O (23.18%)	3/13	2/23	3/13	2/23	11/30	
			M (8.62%)	P (36.55%)							
F	d	21 249	o (42.12%)	s (15.52%)	d (42.36%)	8/19	2/13	11/26			
F	f	2 310	F (42.9%)	e (15.58%)	f (41.52%)	3/7	2/13	12/29			
F	O	10 127	D (41.98%)	S (16.08%)	O (41.95%)	8/19	4/25	8/19			
F	M	3 752	D (41.6%)	S (16.63%)	O (41.76%)	5/12	1/6	5/12			
F	P	28 929	D (23.24%)	S (8.67%)	O (22.61%)	7/30	2/23	5/22	2/23	7/19	
			M (8.61%)	P (36.86%)							
D	p	266 567	p (47.62%)	m (5.19%)	o (22.44%)	10/21	1/19	2/9	1/30	2/9	
			F (2.44%)	D (22.31%)							
D	m	29 816	o (46.81%)	F (5.32%)	D (47.86%)	7/15	1/19	11/23			
D	o	80 022	o (47.63%)	F (5.25%)	D (47.12%)	10/21	1/19	8/17			
D	s	29 622	o (47.46%)	F (5.4%)	D (47.14%)	9/19	1/19	8/17			
D	d	188 932	o (20.02%)	F (2.24%)	D (19.97%)	1/5	1/30	1/5	2/27	0	2/27
			s (7.47%)	e (0.81%)	S (7.43%)				1/5	1/30	1/5
			d (19.85%)	f (2.26%)	O (19.95%)						
D	f	20 911	D (42.23%)	S (15.15%)	O (42.62%)	11/26	3/20	3/7			
D	O	89 668	D (41.97%)	S (15.47%)	O (42.56%)	8/19	2/13	11/26			
D	M	33 698	D (41.98%)	S (15.95%)	O (42.07%)	8/19	4/25	8/19			
D	P	260 012	D (23.03%)	S (8.54%)	O (23.08%)	3/13	2/23	3/13	2/23	7/19	
			M (8.55%)	P (36.81%)							
s	o	41 844	p (53.89%)	m (12.56%)	o (33.56%)	7/13	1/8	1/3			
s	F	4 590	p (53.81%)	m (12.55%)	o (33.64%)	7/13	1/8	1/3			

s	D	59 083	p (37.69%) F (5.57%)	m (8.83%) D (23.7%)	o (24.22%)	3/8 2/23 7/29 1/18 5/21
s	S	11 610	s (44.77%)	e (10.47%)	S (44.76%)	13/29 2/19 13/29
s	O	31 442	d (44.86%)	f (10.54%)	O (44.6%)	13/29 2/19 4/9
S	p	99 764	p (47.08%) F (2.5%)	m (5.23%) D (22.69%)	o (22.51%)	8/17 1/19 5/22 1/30 5/22
S	m	11 130	o (47.72%)	F (5.64%)	D (46.64%)	10/21 1/18 7/15
S	o	29 414	o (47.22%)	F (5.14%)	D (47.64%)	9/19 1/19 10/21
S	s	11 259	s (47.15%)	e (5.57%)	S (47.28%)	8/17 1/18 9/19
S	d	29 879	d (47.28%)	f (5.36%)	O (47.35%)	9/19 1/19 9/19
d	o	163 332	p (36.59%) s (8.65%)	m (8.61%) d (23.19%)	o (22.96%)	11/30 2/23 3/13 2/23 3/13
d	F	18 422	p (36.51%) s (8.79%)	m (8.39%) d (22.9%)	o (23.41%)	4/11 1/12 7/30 2/23 5/22
d	D	346 695	p (17.11%) F (2.6%) e (0.95%) f (2.54%) P (17.17%)	m (4.13%) D (10.86%) S (4.06%) O (10.83%)	o (10.79%) s (3.99%) d (10.95%) M (4.02%)	5/29 1/24 3/28 1/30 3/28 1/25 0 1/25 1/9 1/30 3/28 1/25 5/29
d	S	58 646	d (23.86%) M (8.94%)	f (5.5%) P (38.25%)	O (23.44%)	5/21 1/18 4/17 1/11 8/21
d	O	158 743	d (23.79%) M (8.94%)	f (5.5%) P (37.73%)	O (24.04%)	5/21 1/18 6/25 1/11 11/29
f	o	20 959	o (42.29%)	s (15.87%)	d (41.83%)	11/26 3/19 5/12
f	F	2 332	F (42.45%)	e (14.71%)	f (42.84%)	11/26 4/27 3/7
f	D	18 230	D (22.83%) M (8.63%)	S (8.11%) P (36.73%)	O (23.71%)	5/22 2/25 5/21 2/23 11/30
f	S	4 719	O (34.65%)	M (12.48%)	P (52.87%)	9/26 1/8 9/17
f	O	12 420	O (33.6%)	M (12.79%)	P (53.62%)	1/3 3/23 15/28
O	p	267 112	p (47.34%) F (2.45%)	m (5.29%) D (22.53%)	o (22.39%)	9/19 1/19 2/9 1/30 5/22
O	m	29 461	o (47.49%)	F (5.08%)	D (47.42%)	9/19 1/20 9/19
O	o	189 280	o (19.83%) s (7.5%) d (19.88%)	F (2.2%) e (0.81%) f (2.26%)	D (20%) S (7.45%) O (20.06%)	1/5 1/30 1/5 2/27 0 2/27 1/5 1/30 1/5
O	F	21 199	D (42.33%)	S (15.86%)	O (41.81%)	11/26 3/19 5/12

O	D	164 296	D (23.12%) M (8.69%)	S (8.59%) P (36.52%)	O (23.08%)	3/13 2/23 3/13 2/23 11/30
O	s	29 768	d (47.26%)	f (5.33%)	O (47.41%)	9/19 1/19 9/19
O	S	42 100	O (33.89%)	M (12.9%)	P (53.21%)	1/3 3/23 8/15
O	d	79 749	d (47.77%)	f (5.23%)	O (47%)	11/23 1/19 8/17
O	O	112 146	O (34.02%)	M (12.63%)	P (53.35%)	10/29 1/8 8/15
M	p	98 734	p (47.35%) F (2.4%)	m (5.31%) D (22.36%)	o (22.57%)	9/19 1/19 5/22 1/30 2/9
M	m	11 135	s (47.89%)	e (5.35%)	S (46.76%)	11/23 1/19 7/15
M	o	29 771	d (47.44%)	f (5.33%)	O (47.23%)	9/19 1/19 9/19
M	s	11 089	d (47.67%)	f (5.37%)	O (46.96%)	10/21 1/19 8/17
M	d	29 662	d (47.17%)	f (5.46%)	O (47.36%)	8/17 1/18 9/19
P	p	891 539	p (22.45%) F (1.17%) e (0.28%) f (1.18%) P (22.38%)	m (2.49%) D (10.64%) S (2.5%) O (10.65%)	o (10.65%) s (2.49%) d (10.62%) M (2.51%)	2/9 1/30 3/28 0 3/28 1/30 0 1/30 2/19 0 3/28 1/30 2/9
P	m	99 503	d (22.54%) M (5.26%)	f (2.52%) P (47.38%)	O (22.3%)	5/22 1/30 2/9 1/19 9/19
P	o	267 136	d (22.45%) M (5.29%)	f (2.41%) P (47.45%)	O (22.41%)	2/9 1/30 2/9 1/19 9/19
P	s	98 932	d (22.5%) M (5.27%)	f (2.43%) P (47.56%)	O (22.25%)	5/22 1/30 2/9 1/19 10/21
P	d	266 727	d (22.42%) M (5.24%)	f (2.46%) P (47.47%)	O (22.41%)	2/9 1/30 2/9 1/19 9/19

Table A15: Global relation distribution for $(p, q) = (0.10, 0.01)$

Relation	Name	Count	Probability
o	Overlaps	2 142 722	21.43%
D	Contains	2 140 299	21.40%
O	Overlapped By	2 140 203	21.40%
d	During	2 139 348	21.39%
P	After	391 694	3.92%
p	Before	391 020	3.91%
s	Starts	261 251	2.61%
S	Started By	260 609	2.61%
M	Met By	43 781	0.44%
m	Meets	43 372	0.43%
F	Finished By	21 538	0.22%
f	Finishes	21 531	0.22%
e	Equals	2 632	0.03%

Table A16: Composition table showing multiple outcomes for $(p, q) = (0.10, 0.01)$

r_1	r_2	Total	r_3	Outcomes (rel \rightarrow %)	\approx Fractions
p	d	135 194	p	(19.27%) m (4.52%) o (33.91%) s (8.46%) d (33.84%)	$5/26$ $1/22$ $10/29$ $1/12$ $1/3$
p	f	1 414	p	(18.81%) m (4.6%) o (35.36%) s (7.43%) d (33.8%)	$3/16$ $1/22$ $6/17$ $2/27$ $1/3$
p	O	135 103	p	(19.24%) m (4.5%) o (34.14%) s (8.31%) d (33.81%)	$5/26$ $1/22$ $10/29$ $1/12$ $1/3$
p	M	2 771	p	(19.56%) m (4.51%) o (33.78%) s (8.99%) d (33.16%)	$5/26$ $1/22$ $1/3$ $1/11$ $1/3$
p	P	52 024	p	(9.07%) m (2.21%) o (15.76%) F (2.03%) D (16.19%) s (4.17%) e (0.49%) S (3.89%) d (16.53%) f (1.96%) O (16.2%) M (2.25%) P (9.25%)	$1/11$ $1/30$ $3/19$ $1/30$ $4/25$ $1/24$ 0 $1/26$ $1/6$ $1/30$ $4/25$ $1/30$ $1/11$
m	d	12 563	o	(43.56%) s (11.24%) d (45.2%)	$10/23$ $1/9$ $9/20$
m	f	125	o	(37.6%) s (9.6%) d (52.8%)	$3/8$ $2/21$ $9/17$
m	O	12 572	o	(44.69%) s (10.98%) d (44.33%)	$13/29$ $1/9$ $4/9$

m	M	242	F (44.21%)	e (12.81%)	f (42.98%)	11/25	3/23	3/7
m	P	2 687	D (33.61%) M (4.35%)	S (7.78%) P (18.91%)	O (35.36%)	1/3	1/13	6/17 1/23 4/21
o	o	234 917	p (19.51%)	m (2.34%)	o (78.15%)	5/26	1/30	18/23
o	F	2 326	p (19.39%)	m (2.19%)	o (78.42%)	5/26	1/30	11/14
o	D	422 860	p (10.88%) F (0.89%)	m (1.33%) D (43.42%)	o (43.49%)	3/28	0	10/23 0 10/23
o	S	49 646	o (49.48%)	F (0.96%)	D (49.55%)	1/2	0	1/2
o	d	412 605	o (44.54%)	s (10.92%)	d (44.54%)	4/9	1/9	4/9
o	f	4 169	o (43.87%)	s (10.53%)	d (45.6%)	7/16	2/19	5/11
o	O	832 781	o (22.08%) s (5.42%) d (21.97%)	F (0.45%) e (0.11%) f (0.45%)	D (22.04%) S (5.44%) O (22.04%)	2/9	0	2/9 1/18 0 1/18 5/23 0 2/9
o	M	12 588	D (44.68%)	S (11.07%)	O (44.25%)	13/29	1/9	4/9
o	P	135 727	D (34.05%) M (4.55%)	S (8.33%) P (19.24%)	O (33.82%)	10/29	1/12	1/3 1/22 5/26
F	d	8 398	o (44.5%)	s (11.36%)	d (44.14%)	4/9	3/26	11/25
F	f	81	F (40.74%)	e (9.88%)	f (49.38%)	11/27	1/10	1/2
F	O	4 173	D (43.76%)	S (11.1%)	O (45.15%)	7/16	1/9	9/20
F	M	118	D (38.14%)	S (15.25%)	O (46.61%)	8/21	2/13	7/15
F	P	1 450	D (31.93%) M (4.62%)	S (8.48%) P (20%)	O (34.97%)	8/25	1/12	7/20 1/22 1/5
D	p	102 099	p (8.31%) F (0.48%)	m (0.92%) D (45.36%)	o (44.93%)	1/12	0	9/20 0 5/11
D	m	11 422	o (49.75%)	F (0.54%)	D (49.7%)	1/2	0	1/2
D	o	369 325	o (49.72%)	F (0.5%)	D (49.78%)	1/2	0	1/2
D	s	49 452	o (50.05%)	F (0.46%)	D (49.49%)	1/2	0	1/2
D	d	827 103	o (22.2%) s (5.52%) d (22.05%)	F (0.23%) e (0.05%) f (0.22%)	D (22.21%) S (5.41%) O (22.11%)	2/9	0	2/9 1/18 0 1/18 2/9 0 2/9
D	f	8 277	D (44.68%)	S (10.6%)	O (44.73%)	13/29	2/19	13/29
D	O	410 941	D (44.52%)	S (10.92%)	O (44.55%)	4/9	1/9	4/9
D	M	12 591	D (44.54%)	S (10.92%)	O (44.54%)	4/9	1/9	4/9
D	P	135 395	D (33.84%) M (4.56%)	S (8.45%) P (19.24%)	O (33.92%)	1/3	1/12	10/29 1/22 5/26
s	o	58 089	p (19.65%)	m (2.41%)	o (77.94%)	1/5	1/30	7/9
s	F	568	p (17.61%)	m (1.94%)	o (80.46%)	3/17	1/30	21/26

s	D	104 129	p (10.81%) F (0.87%)	m (1.32%) D (43.49%)	o (43.52%)	3/28 0 10/23 0 10/23
s	S	12 130	s (49.44%)	e (0.98%)	S (49.58%)	1/2 0 1/2
s	O	49 686	d (49.14%)	f (1.01%)	O (49.85%)	1/2 0 1/2
S	p	25 242	p (8.33%) F (0.46%)	m (0.83%) D (45.02%)	o (45.35%)	1/12 0 5/11 0 9/20
S	m	2 765	o (48.32%)	F (0.61%)	D (51.07%)	14/29 0 15/29
S	o	91 085	o (49.58%)	F (0.47%)	D (49.95%)	1/2 0 1/2
S	s	12 170	s (49.88%)	e (0.41%)	S (49.71%)	1/2 0 1/2
S	d	48 909	d (49.47%)	f (0.48%)	O (50.05%)	1/2 0 1/2
d	o	443 063	p (10.38%) s (5.5%)	m (1.27%) d (41.31%)	o (41.55%)	3/29 0 5/12 1/18 12/29
d	F	4 444	p (10.55%) s (5.51%)	m (1.42%) d (41.81%)	o (40.71%)	2/19 0 11/27 1/18 5/12
d	D	895 567	p (5.15%) F (0.4%) e (0.06%) f (0.42%) P (5.15%)	m (0.64%) D (20.52%) S (2.74%) O (20.47%)	o (20.51%) s (2.74%) d (20.56%) M (0.63%)	1/19 0 6/29 0 6/29 1/30 0 1/30 6/29 0 6/29 0 1/19
d	S	104 375	d (43.5%) M (1.37%)	f (0.89%) P (11.01%)	O (43.22%)	10/23 0 13/30 0 1/9
d	O	422 024	d (43.3%) M (1.34%)	f (0.88%) P (10.9%)	O (43.58%)	13/30 0 10/23 0 3/28
f	o	7 875	o (46.39%)	s (6.11%)	d (47.5%)	13/28 1/16 10/21
f	F	86	F (39.53%)	e (5.81%)	f (54.65%)	11/28 1/17 6/11
f	D	4 526	D (41.52%) M (1.19%)	S (5.81%) P (10.25%)	O (41.23%)	12/29 1/17 7/17 0 3/29
f	S	611	O (77.41%)	M (2.45%)	P (20.13%)	17/22 1/30 1/5
f	O	2 375	O (78.61%)	M (2.48%)	P (18.91%)	11/14 1/30 4/21
O	p	101 769	p (8.27%) F (0.45%)	m (0.93%) D (45.11%)	o (45.24%)	1/12 0 5/11 0 9/20
O	m	11 067	o (49.99%)	F (0.47%)	D (49.54%)	1/2 0 1/2
O	o	786 437	o (23.32%) s (3.08%) d (23.36%)	F (0.24%) e (0.03%) f (0.23%)	D (23.33%) S (3.09%) O (23.31%)	7/30 0 7/30 1/30 0 1/30 7/30 0 7/30
O	F	8 050	D (47.63%)	S (6.46%)	O (45.91%)	10/21 1/15 11/24

O	D	441 548	D (41.32%) M (1.25%)	S (5.55%) P (10.38%)	O (41.51%)	12/29 1/18 12/29 0 3/29
O	s	90 942	d (49.64%)	f (0.45%)	O (49.91%)	1/2 0 1/2
O	S	58 098	O (78.18%)	M (2.48%)	P (19.35%)	18/23 1/30 5/26
O	d	369 586	d (49.72%)	f (0.5%)	O (49.78%)	1/2 0 1/2
O	O	235 464	O (78.03%)	M (2.42%)	P (19.55%)	18/23 1/30 5/26
M	p	13 421	p (8.02%) F (0.41%)	m (0.89%) D (45.52%)	o (45.16%)	2/25 0 9/20 0 5/11
M	m	1 498	s (50%)	e (0.67%)	S (49.33%)	1/2 0 1/2
M	o	11 396	d (50.08%)	f (0.46%)	O (49.46%)	1/2 0 1/2
M	s	2 704	d (52.33%)	f (0.59%)	O (47.08%)	11/21 0 8/17
M	d	11 318	d (49.41%)	f (0.48%)	O (50.11%)	1/2 0 1/2
P	p	122 383	p (3.97%) F (0.22%) e (0.03%) f (0.23%) P (3.94%)	m (0.44%) D (21.3%) S (2.62%) O (21.41%)	o (21.49%) s (2.56%) d (21.37%) M (0.44%)	1/25 0 3/14 0 3/14 1/30 0 1/30 3/14 0 3/14 0 1/25
P	m	13 512	d (44.9%) M (1%)	f (0.42%) P (8.44%)	O (45.24%)	13/29 0 5/11 0 1/12
P	o	101 659	d (45.31%) M (0.92%)	f (0.45%) P (8.41%)	O (44.91%)	5/11 0 13/29 0 1/12
P	s	25 210	d (45.37%) M (0.91%)	f (0.48%) P (8.14%)	O (45.1%)	5/11 0 9/20 0 2/25
P	d	101 726	d (45.31%) M (0.94%)	f (0.42%) P (8.24%)	O (45.09%)	5/11 0 9/20 0 1/12

Table A17: Global relation distribution for $(p, q) = (0.01, 0.10)$

Relation	Name	Count	Probability
p	Before	4 518 641	45.19%
P	After	4 517 505	45.18%
o	Overlaps	195 264	1.95%
O	Overlapped By	195 188	1.95%
D	Contains	194 542	1.95%
d	During	194 204	1.94%
m	Meets	45 889	0.46%
M	Met By	45 390	0.45%
S	Started By	23 774	0.24%
s	Starts	23 643	0.24%
F	Finished By	21 766	0.22%
f	Finishes	21 623	0.22%
e	Equals	2 571	0.03%

Table A18: Composition table showing multiple outcomes for $(p, q) = (0.01, 0.10)$

r_1	r_2	Total	r_3 Outcomes (rel \rightarrow %)	\approx Fractions
p	d	63 780	p (83.51%) m (1.84%) o (6.87%) s (0.95%) d (6.83%)	$\frac{5}{6} \frac{1}{30} \frac{2}{29} 0 \frac{2}{29}$
p	f	7 247	p (83.37%) m (1.72%) o (6.82%) s (0.94%) d (7.15%)	$\frac{5}{6} \frac{1}{30} \frac{2}{29} 0 \frac{1}{14}$
p	O	64 400	p (83.71%) m (1.78%) o (6.75%) s (0.93%) d (6.82%)	$\frac{21}{25} \frac{1}{30} \frac{1}{15} 0 \frac{2}{29}$
p	M	15 161	p (83.81%) m (1.64%) o (6.69%) s (1%) d (6.86%)	$\frac{21}{25} 0 \frac{1}{15} 0 \frac{2}{29}$
p	P	2 991 843	p (41.44%) m (0.84%) o (3.43%) F (0.42%) D (3.39%) s (0.45%) e (0.06%) S (0.45%) d (3.4%) f (0.42%) O (3.42%) M (0.83%) P (41.44%)	$\frac{12}{29} 0 \frac{1}{29} 0 \frac{1}{29} 0 0 0 \frac{1}{29} 0 \frac{1}{29}$ $0 \frac{12}{29}$
m	d	1 180	o (47.63%) s (4.83%) d (47.54%)	$\frac{10}{21} \frac{1}{21} \frac{10}{21}$
m	f	131	o (50.38%) s (3.82%) d (45.8%)	$\frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{26} \frac{11}{24}$
m	O	1 135	o (46.78%) s (6.96%) d (46.26%)	$\frac{7}{15} \frac{2}{29} \frac{6}{13}$

m	M	226	F (49.12%)	e (7.96%)	f (42.92%)	14/29	2/25	3/7
m	P	14 858	D (6.94%) M (1.56%)	S (0.93%) P (83.49%)	O (7.08%)	2/29	0 1/14	0 5/6
o	o	6 420	p (68.29%)	m (8.52%)	o (23.19%)	15/22	2/23	3/13
o	F	722	p (67.87%)	m (9.56%)	o (22.58%)	19/28	2/21	5/22
o	D	8 274	p (53.69%) F (3.98%)	m (7.12%) D (17.66%)	o (17.56%)	15/28	1/14	3/17 1/25 3/17
o	S	858	o (46.04%)	F (11.42%)	D (42.54%)	6/13	3/26	11/26
o	d	3 065	o (47.5%)	s (5.71%)	d (46.79%)	10/21	1/18	7/15
o	f	355	o (45.92%)	s (7.32%)	d (46.76%)	11/24	2/27	7/15
o	O	7 087	o (21.01%) s (2.85%) d (20.98%)	F (5.19%) e (0.76%) f (4.67%)	D (20.64%) S (3.06%) O (20.83%)	4/19	1/19	6/29 1/30 0 1/30 4/19 1/21 5/24
o	M	1 142	D (46.5%)	S (7.71%)	O (45.8%)	13/28	1/13	11/24
o	P	64 483	D (6.87%) M (1.65%)	S (0.97%) P (83.67%)	O (6.85%)	2/29	0 2/29	0 21/25
F	d	771	o (48.9%)	s (5.97%)	d (45.14%)	14/29	1/17	9/20
F	f	90	F (51.11%)	e (1.11%)	f (47.78%)	15/29	0	11/23
F	O	354	D (46.61%)	S (6.5%)	O (46.89%)	7/15	1/15	8/17
F	M	140	D (47.86%)	S (7.14%)	O (45%)	11/23	1/14	9/20
F	P	7 105	D (6.88%) M (1.7%)	S (0.83%) P (83.76%)	O (6.83%)	2/29	0 2/29	1/30 21/25
D	p	111 764	p (90.83%) F (0.45%)	m (0.91%) D (3.83%)	o (3.97%)	10/11	0 1/25	0 1/26
D	m	1 120	o (45.36%)	F (4.73%)	D (49.91%)	5/11	1/21	1/2
D	o	3 096	o (46.67%)	F (5.14%)	D (48.19%)	7/15	1/19	13/27
D	s	772	o (49.61%)	F (5.7%)	D (44.69%)	1/2	1/18	13/29
D	d	6 542	o (21.31%) s (2.92%) d (21.6%)	F (2.52%) e (0.44%) f (2.14%)	D (23.07%) S (2.93%) O (23.07%)	3/14	1/30	3/13 1/30 0 1/30 5/23 1/30 3/13
D	f	754	D (45.62%)	S (6.5%)	O (47.88%)	5/11	1/15	11/23
D	O	3 073	D (46.4%)	S (5.99%)	O (47.61%)	13/28	1/17	10/21
D	M	1 137	D (46.79%)	S (5.63%)	O (47.58%)	7/15	1/18	10/21
D	P	63 608	D (6.86%) M (1.69%)	S (0.86%) P (83.78%)	O (6.81%)	2/29	0 2/29	1/30 21/25
s	o	886	p (68.4%)	m (9.14%)	o (22.46%)	13/19	1/11	2/9
s	F	98	p (70.41%)	m (8.16%)	o (21.43%)	19/27	2/25	3/14

s	D	1 042	p (54.22%) F (4.41%)	m (7.58%) D (17.66%)	o (16.12%)	13/24 1/13 4/25 1/23 3/17
s	S	103	s (34.95%)	e (6.8%)	S (58.25%)	7/20 2/29 7/12
s	O	774	d (43.67%)	f (9.3%)	O (47.03%)	7/16 1/11 8/17
S	p	14 968	p (91.16%) F (0.43%)	m (0.82%) D (3.88%)	o (3.7%)	21/23 0 1/27 0 1/26
S	m	139	o (52.52%)	F (5.04%)	D (42.45%)	10/19 1/20 11/26
S	o	408	o (47.06%)	F (5.64%)	D (47.3%)	8/17 1/18 9/19
S	s	97	s (44.33%)	e (4.12%)	S (51.55%)	4/9 1/24 15/29
S	d	774	d (46.77%)	f (4.13%)	O (49.1%)	7/15 1/24 14/29
d	o	8 072	p (53.32%) s (4.21%)	m (6.55%) d (17.63%)	o (18.29%)	8/15 1/15 2/11 1/24 3/17
d	F	909	p (53.03%) s (3.41%)	m (7.26%) d (18.7%)	o (17.6%)	9/17 1/14 3/17 1/29 3/16
d	D	17 326	p (25.25%) F (1.93%) e (0.48%) f (2.06%) P (25.89%)	m (3.17%) D (8.44%) S (2.12%) O (8.5%)	o (8.36%) s (2%) d (8.77%) M (3.03%)	1/4 1/30 1/12 1/30 1/12 1/30 0 1/30 2/23 1/30 1/12 1/30 7/27
d	S	1 098	d (16.39%) M (7.29%)	f (4.64%) P (53.01%)	O (18.67%)	1/6 1/22 3/16 2/27 9/17
d	O	8 188	d (17.75%) M (6.77%)	f (4.02%) P (54.09%)	O (17.38%)	3/17 1/25 4/23 1/15 13/24
f	o	744	o (45.03%)	s (13.04%)	d (41.94%)	9/20 3/23 8/19
f	F	76	F (44.74%)	e (10.53%)	f (44.74%)	13/29 2/19 13/29
f	D	938	D (18.76%) M (5.33%)	S (4.48%) P (54.58%)	O (16.84%)	3/16 1/22 1/6 1/19 6/11
f	S	92	O (27.17%)	M (7.61%)	P (65.22%)	3/11 1/13 15/23
f	O	693	O (22.22%)	M (7.94%)	P (69.84%)	2/9 2/25 7/10
O	p	112 516	p (90.86%) F (0.45%)	m (0.9%) D (3.91%)	o (3.88%)	10/11 0 1/26 0 1/26
O	m	1 108	o (44.95%)	F (4.42%)	D (50.63%)	9/20 1/23 1/2
O	o	6 859	o (20.91%) s (4.94%) d (20.94%)	F (2.43%) e (0.51%) f (2.38%)	D (21.27%) S (5.61%) O (21.01%)	5/24 1/30 3/14 1/20 0 1/18 5/24 1/30 4/19
O	F	723	D (45.5%)	S (11.62%)	O (42.88%)	5/11 3/26 3/7

O	D	8 159	D (18.04%) M (6.67%)	S (4.53%) P (53.23%)	O (17.53%)	2/11 1/22 3/17 1/15 8/15
O	s	401	d (45.89%)	f (6.23%)	O (47.88%)	11/24 1/16 11/23
O	S	856	O (22.78%)	M (10.4%)	P (66.82%)	5/22 3/29 2/3
O	d	3 055	d (47.53%)	f (5.04%)	O (47.43%)	10/21 1/20 9/19
O	O	6 267	O (21.64%)	M (8.44%)	P (69.92%)	5/23 1/12 7/10
M	p	27 886	p (90.95%) F (0.43%)	m (0.98%) D (3.94%)	o (3.7%)	10/11 0 1/27 0 1/25
M	m	268	s (46.64%)	e (3.73%)	S (49.63%)	7/15 1/27 1/2
M	o	1 083	d (47.83%)	f (5.72%)	O (46.45%)	11/23 1/17 13/28
M	s	149	d (41.61%)	f (4.03%)	O (54.36%)	5/12 1/25 6/11
M	d	1 174	d (46.85%)	f (5.11%)	O (48.04%)	7/15 1/20 12/25
P	p	2 744 424	p (45.19%) F (0.22%) e (0.02%) f (0.22%) P (45.2%)	m (0.45%) D (1.95%) S (0.24%) O (1.94%)	o (1.94%) s (0.24%) d (1.94%) M (0.46%)	9/20 0 1/30 0 1/30 0 0 0 1/30 0 1/30 0 9/20
P	m	27 893	d (3.91%) M (0.8%)	f (0.35%) P (91.12%)	O (3.81%)	1/26 0 1/26 0 21/23
P	o	112 600	d (3.86%) M (0.91%)	f (0.44%) P (90.78%)	O (4.01%)	1/26 0 1/25 0 10/11
P	s	14 945	d (3.61%) M (0.84%)	f (0.51%) P (90.91%)	O (4.14%)	1/28 0 1/24 0 10/11
P	d	112 276	d (3.92%) M (0.95%)	f (0.44%) P (90.86%)	O (3.83%)	1/25 0 1/26 0 10/11

Table A19: Global relation distribution for $(p, q) = (0.01, 0.01)$

Relation	Name	Count	Probability
P	After	2 476 611	24.77%
p	Before	2 474 901	24.75%
D	Contains	1 231 879	12.32%
d	During	1 230 654	12.31%
O	Overlapped By	1 230 448	12.30%
o	Overlaps	1 230 444	12.30%
M	Met By	25 054	0.25%
s	Starts	24 960	0.25%
S	Started By	24 925	0.25%
m	Meets	24 793	0.25%
f	Finishes	12 717	0.13%
F	Finished By	12 378	0.12%
e	Equals	236	0.00%

Table A20: Composition table showing multiple outcomes for $(p, q) = (0.01, 0.01)$

r_1	r_2	Total	r_3 Outcomes (rel \rightarrow %)	\approx Fractions
p	d	316 696	p (42.25%) m (0.85%) o (28.03%) s (0.85%) d (28.02%)	$11/26$ 0 $7/25$ 0 $7/25$
p	f	3 195	p (42.72%) m (0.69%) o (28.11%) s (0.81%) d (27.67%)	$3/7$ 0 $7/25$ 0 $8/29$
p	O	316 244	p (42.23%) m (0.85%) o (28.04%) s (0.85%) d (28.02%)	$11/26$ 0 $7/25$ 0 $7/25$
p	M	6 287	p (43.33%) m (0.76%) o (27.99%) s (0.78%) d (27.14%)	$13/30$ 0 $7/25$ 0 $3/11$
p	P	1 282 147	p (21.03%) m (0.42%) o (13.94%) F (0.28%) D (13.96%) s (0.43%) e (<0.01%) S (0.43%) d (13.92%) f (0.29%) O (13.94%) M (0.43%) P (20.95%)	$4/19$ 0 $4/29$ 0 $4/29$ 0 0 0 $4/29$ 0 $4/29$ 0 $4/19$
m	d	3 763	o (48.92%) s (1.36%) d (49.72%)	$14/29$ 0 $1/2$
m	f	42	o (64.29%) s (2.38%) d (33.33%)	$9/14$ $1/30$ $1/3$
m	O	3 752	o (48.35%) s (1.47%) d (50.19%)	$14/29$ 0 $1/2$

m	M	65	F (35.38%)	e (3.08%)	f (61.54%)	6/17	1/30	8/13						
m	P	6 417	D (26.69%)	S (1.08%)	O (28.05%)	4/15	0	7/25	0	13/30				
			M (0.89%)	P (43.29%)										
o	o	150 227	p (59.34%)	m (1.17%)	o (39.48%)	16/27	0	11/28						
o	F	1 450	p (59.38%)	m (1.03%)	o (39.59%)	16/27	0	11/28						
o	D	210 162	p (42.43%)	m (0.84%)	o (27.91%)	11/26	0	7/25	0	7/25				
			F (0.57%)	D (28.24%)										
o	S	3 684	o (48.78%)	F (1%)	D (50.22%)	14/29	0	1/2						
o	d	119 458	o (49.28%)	s (1.48%)	d (49.24%)	1/2	0	1/2						
o	f	1 256	o (47.37%)	s (1.43%)	d (51.19%)	9/19	0	15/29						
o	O	242 057	o (24.38%)	F (0.49%)	D (24.51%)	7/29	0	7/29	0	0	0	7/29	0	7/29
			s (0.74%)	e (0.01%)	S (0.72%)									
			d (24.29%)	f (0.51%)	O (24.34%)									
o	M	3 650	D (49.07%)	S (1.73%)	O (49.21%)	14/29	1/30	1/2						
o	P	317 393	D (28.13%)	S (0.84%)	O (28.02%)	7/25	0	7/25	0	8/19				
			M (0.85%)	P (42.15%)										
F	d	2 382	o (48.61%)	s (1.18%)	d (50.21%)	14/29	0	1/2						
F	f	17	F (70.59%)	f (29.41%)		12/17	5/17							
F	O	1 194	D (48.16%)	S (1.84%)	O (50%)	13/27	1/30	1/2						
F	M	44	D (54.55%)	S (2.27%)	O (43.18%)	6/11	1/30	13/30						
F	P	3 225	D (27.6%)	S (0.68%)	O (29.18%)	8/29	0	7/24	0	5/12				
			M (0.81%)	P (41.74%)										
D	p	359 659	p (49.68%)	m (0.5%)	o (24.78%)	1/2	0	1/4	0	1/4				
			F (0.26%)	D (24.78%)										
D	m	3 461	o (49.61%)	F (0.49%)	D (49.9%)	1/2	0	1/2						
D	o	117 604	o (49.86%)	F (0.49%)	D (49.66%)	1/2	0	1/2						
D	s	3 557	o (48.55%)	F (0.45%)	D (51%)	14/29	0	15/29						
D	d	239 618	o (24.52%)	F (0.24%)	D (24.57%)	7/29	0	7/29	0	0	0	7/29	0	7/29
			s (0.77%)	e (<0.01%)	S (0.75%)									
			d (24.4%)	f (0.24%)	O (24.5%)									
D	f	2 451	D (49.61%)	S (1.22%)	O (49.16%)	1/2	0	1/2						
D	O	119 531	D (49.29%)	S (1.49%)	O (49.22%)	1/2	0	1/2						
D	M	3 550	D (49.07%)	S (1.21%)	O (49.72%)	14/29	0	1/2						
D	P	317 816	D (27.93%)	S (0.86%)	O (28.08%)	7/25	0	7/25	0	11/26				
			M (0.86%)	P (42.28%)										
s	o	4 550	p (59.16%)	m (1.19%)	o (39.65%)	13/22	0	2/5						
s	F	45	p (48.89%)	o (51.11%)		14/29	15/29							

s	D	6 560	p (42.27%) F (0.56%)	m (0.84%) D (28.14%)	o (28.19%)	11/26 0 7/25 0 7/25
s	S	110	s (54.55%)	e (2.73%)	S (42.73%)	6/11 1/30 3/7
s	O	3 635	d (47.84%)	f (0.96%)	O (51.2%)	11/23 0 15/29
S	p	10 911	p (49.78%) F (0.25%)	m (0.46%) D (24.8%)	o (24.72%)	1/2 0 1/4 0 1/4
S	m	130	o (44.62%)	F (0.77%)	D (54.62%)	4/9 0 6/11
S	o	3 631	o (48.61%)	F (0.36%)	D (51.03%)	14/29 0 15/29
S	s	117	s (47.01%)	S (52.99%)		8/17 9/17
S	d	3 656	d (49.54%)	f (0.71%)	O (49.75%)	1/2 0 1/2
d	o	210 922	p (42.15%) s (0.87%)	m (0.82%) d (28.07%)	o (28.08%)	8/19 0 7/25 0 7/25
d	F	2 159	p (42.7%) s (0.69%)	m (0.79%) d (25.2%)	o (30.62%)	3/7 0 4/13 0 1/4
d	D	424 944	p (21.03%) F (0.28%) e (<0.01%) f (0.28%) P (20.99%)	m (0.42%) D (13.9%) S (0.43%) O (13.9%)	o (13.87%) s (0.42%) d (14.06%) M (0.42%)	4/19 0 4/29 0 4/29 0 0 0 1/7 0 4/29 0 4/19
d	S	6 379	d (28.84%) M (0.72%)	f (0.44%) P (41.95%)	O (28.05%)	2/7 0 7/25 0 8/19
d	O	210 494	d (27.85%) M (0.88%)	f (0.59%) P (42.57%)	O (28.12%)	5/18 0 7/25 0 11/26
f	o	2 458	o (47.97%)	s (1.55%)	d (50.49%)	12/25 0 1/2
f	F	34	F (47.06%)	f (52.94%)		8/17 9/17
f	D	2 121	D (29%) M (1.08%)	S (1.13%) P (43.05%)	O (25.74%)	7/24 0 7/27 0 3/7
f	S	50	O (46%)	M (2%)	P (52%)	6/13 1/30 13/25
f	O	1 525	O (40.39%)	M (0.98%)	P (58.62%)	11/27 0 17/29
O	p	359 234	p (49.74%) F (0.25%)	m (0.5%) D (24.78%)	o (24.73%)	1/2 0 1/4 0 1/4
O	m	3 572	o (50.53%)	F (0.36%)	D (49.1%)	1/2 0 14/29
O	o	241 070	o (24.4%) s (0.79%) d (24.65%)	F (0.25%) e (0.01%) f (0.25%)	D (24.46%) S (0.74%) O (24.45%)	7/29 0 7/29 0 0 0 1/4 0 7/29
O	F	2 407	D (51.39%)	S (1.12%)	O (47.49%)	15/29 0 9/19

O	D	211 034	D (27.97%)	S (0.85%)	O (27.95%)	$7/25$	0	$7/25$	0	$11/26$
			M (0.84%)	P (42.39%)						
O	s	3 617	d (48.41%)	f (0.75%)	O (50.84%)	$14/29$	0	$1/2$		
O	S	4 630	O (39.33%)	M (1.02%)	P (59.65%)	$11/28$	0	$3/5$		
O	d	118 613	d (49.79%)	f (0.5%)	O (49.71%)	$1/2$	0	$1/2$		
O	O	148 892	O (39.42%)	M (1.18%)	P (59.4%)	$11/28$	0	$16/27$		
M	p	10 874	p (49.51%)	m (0.53%)	o (24.35%)	$1/2$	0	$7/29$	0	$1/4$
			F (0.22%)	D (25.38%)						
M	m	116	s (47.41%)	e (0.86%)	S (51.72%)	$9/19$	0	$15/29$		
M	o	3 545	d (49.7%)	f (0.34%)	O (49.96%)	$1/2$	0	$1/2$		
M	s	107	d (52.34%)	f (0.93%)	O (46.73%)	$11/21$	0	$7/15$		
M	d	3 614	d (50.17%)	f (0.58%)	O (49.25%)	$1/2$	0	$1/2$		
P	p	1 089 745	p (24.71%)	m (0.26%)	o (12.34%)	$1/4$	0	$1/8$	0	$1/8$ 0 0 0 $1/8$ 0 $1/8$ 0 $1/4$
			F (0.12%)	D (12.32%)	s (0.25%)					
			e (<0.01%)	S (0.25%)	d (12.32%)					
			f (0.13%)	O (12.31%)	M (0.26%)					
			P (24.73%)							
P	m	11 012	d (24.84%)	f (0.2%)	O (24.94%)	$1/4$	0	$1/4$	0	$1/2$
			M (0.48%)	P (49.55%)						
P	o	359 520	d (24.58%)	f (0.27%)	O (24.77%)	$1/4$	0	$1/4$	0	$1/2$
			M (0.52%)	P (49.86%)						
P	s	10 901	d (24.85%)	f (0.17%)	O (25.01%)	$1/4$	0	$1/4$	0	$1/2$
			M (0.51%)	P (49.45%)						
P	d	359 071	d (24.84%)	f (0.27%)	O (24.6%)	$1/4$	0	$1/4$	0	$1/2$
			M (0.5%)	P (49.78%)						

A gentle nod to the complexity of temporal logic.